

Modular Construction of Topologically Complex Polycyclic Acetals by Tether-Controlled Domino Reactions

Rafael R. Castillo, Valentina Abet, Maurizio Aquino, Zoila Gandara, Pascal Retailleau and
Siméon Arseniyadis*

Centre de Recherche de Gif, Institut de Chimie des Substances Naturelles, CNRS, F-91198 Gif-sur-Yvette Cedex (France)

simeon.arseniyadis@icsn.cnrs-gif.fr

Abstract

Pb(OAc)₄ mediated oxidative cleavage of octalin-diols (**1**, **1'**), tethered by variously substituted arenes placed at the angular position (C11), shows switchable regioselectivity effects. A highly selective set of regiochemical outcomes can be achieved, producing a range of polycyclic acetals through competing domino paths (A-E). The modular complexity inherent in the type-**1** domino precursors is derived from the C11 configuration, where the course of ring forming processes is controlled from the chirality at a remote stereocenter (C11). For methylene tethered type-**1'** precursors, the regiochemical outcome is mainly determined by controlling the reaction parameters.

Keywords: domino reactions / molecular complexity / lead tetraacetate / iodobenzene diacetate / microwave acceleration / Friedel-Crafts cycloalkylation

Scheme TOC. One-pot domino pathways to polycyclic acetals: The orientation control is offered by the substitution pattern at C11 as well as on the aromatic ring and by the reaction conditions, which triggers one out of five domino paths (A to E).

Introduction

The presence of a suitable substituent at the angular position in octalin-diols offers a convenient handle for generation of complexity by oxidative techniques. Structurally dissimilar products could be reached selectively in a single synthetic operation, in spite of the similarities in the starting compounds, which differ only in the tether. The outcomes are driven by the substitution pattern, the domino promoter or the solvent used under either conventional or microwave assisted conditions.^[1] Our investigations resulted in efficient ways to construct complex molecular frameworks in one-pot by planned combination of reactive groups placed at the angular position. Thus, it is possible to select a ring-expanding path,^[2] a hetero[4 π +2 π +2 π]cycloaddition,^[3] a ring-retentive oxonium path^[4] a hetero[4+3+2]cycloaddition^[5] by varying the functional group at the angular position or simply to interrupt the process at the [4 π +2 π] stage.^[6] Establishing a basic mechanistic understanding in these domino reactions,^[7] discovered by serendipity, led to the development of new variations and improved our capacity to predict reactivity.

A recent report from our laboratory identified a two-step all-domino protocol for the synthesis of various polycyclic frameworks bearing fascinating architectures.^[8] In the first step, Pb(OAc)₄ mediated oxidative cleavage generates high molecular complexity, while in a subsequent step a hard Lewis acid mediated nucleophilic acetal opening serves as a making sense operation. In generating complexity, advantage is taken of the remarkable ability of Pb(OAc)₄ to act as an oxidizer and as a soft Lewis acid in one reaction vessel, as well as the influence of the angular substituent at C11.^[9] In making sense of generated complexity, topographic outcomes of the first step provide a firm basis for modular selective transformations.

At the outset, the idea was to introduce an angular substituent, the configuration of which could bias the geometry of the transition state leading to the key oxygen or carbon mediated deplumbation (Scheme 1). Consequently, we projected that pre-setting the C11 carbinol configuration in type-1 series or choosing the appropriate domino conditions in type-1' series, could raise the probability of its reacting by neighbouring group participation in the desired sense. The leadtetraacetate-promoted modular domino reactions entail the transient organolead formation (**ii-v**) through a sequence involving initial complexation by the soft Lewis acid Pb(OAc)₄ to the soft π -base enol-ether (**2, 2'**). Product formation could be rationalized by a hetero[4 π +2 π]cycloaddition following an oxidative cleavage, which triggers the (oxy)plumbation. The mode of deplumbation then sets the final destination. Schemes 1, 5 and 7 suggest how six different domino products arise in the Pb(OAc)₄ mediated oxidative cleavage, through paths A–E. Based on the proposed mechanism (Scheme 1), we could expect that the C11(*S**) carbinol configuration would circumvent displacement of lead triacetate at C4 by the angular alkoxy group and thus direct the completion of the skeletal reorganization towards the path A domino product **3**. The key

requirement for path A is that the aromatic ring is sufficiently nucleophilic to displace the $\text{Pb}(\text{OAc})_3$ via a C11 configuration that allows for C13-C4 bonding. It is clear that the transient organolead intermediate **ii** must be able to approximate the orbital alignment requirements and must comply with the requisite nearness of the C4-C13 carbon centers. Accordingly, in the C11(R^*) carbinol series the dominant reaction pathway, after generation of the transient organolead intermediate **iii**, is the production of a cyclic trialkyloxonium intermediate in an entropy-controlled step that collapses to type-4 domino product.

Scheme 1. Tether-controlled reactivity in competing domino processes: Following the $[4\pi + 2\pi]$ cycloaddition, the nature of C11 substituent sets the final destination; path A (**3**) versus path B (**4**) domino products *via* configuration control, path C versus path D via arene substitution and reaction conditions. [a] $\text{Pb}(\text{OAc})_4$ in AcOH, MW irr. 5 min at 90 °C. [b] $\text{Pb}(\text{OAc})_4$ in AcOH, 6-12 h at 25 °C or MW irr. 5 min at 90 °C. [c] $\text{Pb}(\text{OAc})_4$ in CH_2Cl_2 -AcOH (2:1), 20 h at 25 °C. [d] $\text{Pb}(\text{OAc})_4$ in AcOH, MW irr. 5 min at 70 °C.

In the methylene-tethered type-1' series, a suitably placed arene could initiate an effective Friedel-Crafts cyclisation (Path C) at room temperature, affording type-5 domino products even when the arene is unactivated. As the nature of the angular substituent is a controlling factor, in the absence of an

oxygen path C domino process should win over the ring-expansion (path D) when the arene moiety is activated, since the latter is well positioned to interrupt the C10-C4 migration. The ring-expanded type-6 domino product could only be observed in the absence of activating groups on the aromatic moiety. Scheme 1 summarizes the various paths, based on appropriate variation of the substitution pattern and reaction conditions. Path E, which will be discussed later, is not included in Scheme 1, since the results are at odds with the oxyplumbation/deplumbation sequence observed in all published domino reactions thus far.^[1-6] Herein, we report in full the results of this investigation focusing on extending the scope of the oxidative-cleavage triggered modular domino reaction and in the following paper, we present the subsequent elaboration of the domino products to a range of fused/bridged ring systems.

Results and Discussion

Assembling the Domino Precursors. The probe of the present study is the angularly substituted bicyclic ene-diol represented by **1/1'**,^[10] readily prepared by procedures described earlier as summarized in Scheme 2. The known *bis*-TBS-protected aldehyde **7**^(ref. 3) was the starting point for the synthesis of the requisite domino precursors, prepared by a three-step procedure for **1a-k**: addition of a commercially available Grignard or organolithium reagent, followed by MOM-protection of the resulting carbinol and desilylation.^[11] A slightly modified sequence, including xanthate formation and a subsequent deoxygenation was used for the **1'** series (c, d, f, i).

Scheme 2. Preparation of substrate-diols **1** and **1'**.

Carbinol-tethered probes

Working under the hypothesis that attaching an electron-donor bearing aromatic group at C11 would enhance the tendency of C13 to undergo Friedel-Crafts type C-C bonding, we studied the behavior of methoxy and methyl derivatives **1a-k** under the conventional room temperature (rt) and microwave (MW) assisted domino conditions.^[12] The fulfillment of the objectives displayed in Scheme 1 requires

either that we are able to synthesize the C-11 epimerically pure domino probes of type **1** in some reasonable way or that the domino products **3-4**, obtained in mixture depending either upon the original C11 R^*/S^* ratio (**3**, **4**) or reaction conditions, are easily separable. We have at present been able to generate the stereochemically pure C11-carbinols by direct chromatographic separation of the starting diastereomeric mixtures or by conversion to the half-cascade mixture (11 R^* , S^*)-**2**, using PhI(OAc)₂ as the domino promoter and chromatographic separation.^[13] While separation of C11 epimers was achieved by chromatography at either the starting diol (**1**) or the half-cascade stage (**2**) as mentioned above, support for configuration assignment was secured from single-crystal X-ray determination of (11 R^*)-**2c**, (11 S^*)-**2e** and (11 R^*)-**2f** (Figure 1)^[8] and served to define the configuration at C11 on all half-cascade type-2 domino products.

Figure 1. X-ray structures of “interrupted-domino” products (11 R^*)-**2c** and (11 S^*)-**2e**.

An added challenge was the formation of type (11 S^*)-**4** species, obtained only under specific conditions, with the ultimate aim to study their behavior towards various silicon containing nucleophiles in Lewis acid activated acetal ring opening reactions. Towards this goal, we noticed that temperature and time played a determining role in domino product distribution. Heating the reaction mixture led to a dramatic increase in rate of formation of the type-**3** product, while in the absence of microwave heating extended reaction times were needed for its formation. However, under such conditions, some (11 S^*)-**4** was also produced in competition with **3** (Table 1). Thus, applying prolonged reaction time (6-16 h) on (11 R^* , S^*)-**1** at room temperature always leads to a competitive formation of (11 S^*)-**4** along with the expected domino products **3** and (11 R^*)-**4**. On the other hand, subjecting (11 R^* , S^*)-**1** to rt-domino conditions for a maximum of 5 h, no path A domino product (**3**) was observed leaving its precursor, the (11 S^*) configured half-cascade **2**, epimerically pure. Eventually, we determined the most effective conditions for the selective formation of the type-(11 R^*)-**4** series to be the rt stirring. This mild procedure provided good yields of the (11 R^*)-**4** domino product along with the (11 S^*)-**2** half-cascade product, which were easily separated *via* flash chromatography. The feasibility of such an approach was examined with the use of several substrate-diols (**1b,c,d**, Table 1).

entry	Time	(11R*)-2	(11S*)-2	3	(11R*)-4	(11S*)-4
1	16 h	—	—	3b (12%)	(11R*)-4b (52%)	(11S*)-4b (9%)
2	<5 h	—	(11S*)-2b (17%)	—	(11R*)-4b (65%)	—
3		—	(11S*)-2c (27%)	—	(11R*)-4c (48%)	—
4		—	(11S*)-2d (34%)	—	(11R*)-4d (29%)	—
5	16 h	—	—	3b (44%)	—	(11S*)-4b (33%)
6	(11S*)-2	—	—	3c (58%)	—	(11S*)-4c (5%)
7		—	—	3d (61%)	—	(11S*)-4d (24%)

Table 1. Temperature and time as additional pathway control factors of domino reactions. Looking for reaction conditions to ensure formation of (11S*)-4.

As an exploratory study^[14] of the proposed domino process for the preparation of polycyclic acetal derivatives, we first carried out a series of experiments by reacting substrate diols of type (11S*)-1 and (11R*)-1, obtained epimerically pure, with Pb(OAc)₄ in AcOH under microwave heating (90 °C, 5 min). Each underwent a remarkable skeletal rearrangement to give the corresponding **3** and **4**, respectively, as the result of oxidative cleavage followed by consecutive cyclizations (Scheme 3). Using PhI(OAc)₂ as the domino promoter in MeCN at room temperature, epimerically pure half-cascade intermediates of type (11S*)-2 and (11R*)-2 were cleanly obtained and characterized, serving as mechanistic probes for distinguishing the domino pathways. The path selectivities for the (11R*) and (11S*) series are portrayed in Scheme 3.

Scheme 3. Proof of concept experiments: 11S* triggers path A while 11R* triggers path B.

Isolation of either domino product **3** or **4** as single product provided convincing support for an orientation control offered by the stereogenic center C11, which triggers either the path A or the path B. The structural assignment to the path A domino products **3**, rests firmly on spectroscopic grounds with HMBC studies proving particularly informative. Expressly, HMBC correlations observed from the C11 carbon to the C3 proton (and C3 to C11H), as well as C12 and C14 to C4 proton, established the connectivity of these two cyclic residues indicating C4-C13 and C11O-C3 bonding. X-ray crystallography (**3b**, **3c**, and **3e**)^[8] further corroborated the proposed structure **3**, showing that the (11*S**) configuration was required to insure this domino path.

Using random diastereomeric mixtures of domino precursors, the relative proportions of the domino products obtained in mixture (according to starting C11 epimeric ratios) were easily determined by integration of characteristic resonances. As a general rule, path A (oxidative/pericyclic/Friedel-Crafts) type domino products **3a-h** showed anomeric proton H-3 resonances upfield ($\delta \approx 5.5$ ppm) of the corresponding resonances for path B type domino products **4a-h** ($\delta > 6.1$ ppm). Integration of these resonances, on the crude reaction mixtures, was used to determine the regioselectivities of the reactions reported in Table 2.

Entry	C11-config assignment (yield %, dr)	Substrate diol	Entry	Path A Product (yield %)	Path B Product (yield %)
1	(11 <i>R</i> * <i>S</i> *)-2a (85%, 3.3:1)	1a R ² = OMe, R ¹ = R ³ = H	9	3a (15%)	4a (48%)
2	(11 <i>R</i> * <i>S</i> *)-2b (92%, 1:1.4)	1b R ¹ = R ² = H, R ³ = OMe	10	3b (44%)	4b (33%)
3	(11 <i>R</i> * <i>S</i> *)-2c (90%, 1:2.5)	1c R ¹ = R ³ = OMe, R ² = H	11	3c (44%)	4c (21%)
4	(11 <i>R</i> * <i>S</i> *)-2d (98%, 1:1.3)	1d R ¹ = R ² = R ³ = OMe	12	3d (50%)	4d (22%)
5	(11 <i>R</i> * <i>S</i> *)-2e (97%, 1.4:1)	1e R ¹ = H, R ² = R ³ = OCH ₂ O	13	3e (30%)	4e (56%) ^[a]
6	(11 <i>R</i> * <i>S</i> *)-2f (95%, 1.3:1)	1f R ¹ = R ³ = Me, R ² = H	14	3f (20%)	4f (60%)
7	(11 <i>R</i> * <i>S</i> *)-2g (94%, 1:1)	1g R ¹ = H, R ² = R ³ = OMe	15	3g (42%)	4g (41%)
8	(11 <i>R</i> * <i>S</i> *)-2h (91%, 2.3:1)	1h R ¹ = R ³ = Me, R ² = OMe	16	3h (25%)	4h (53%)

Table 2. All reactions on substrate diols **1** (1 equiv), in the indicated solvent (5.0 mL/mmol), were run under the following conditions. Interrupted domino process for epimer ratio measurement and configuration assignment: PhI(OAc)₂ (1.1 equiv) in MeCN, at 25 °C. Full domino process: Pb(OAc)₄ (2.4 equiv) in AcOH, MW irr. 5 min at 90 °C. [a] Some acetal deprotection was observed, lowering the isolated yields.

When **1a** (diastereomeric mixture with a C11*R**/*S** ratio of 3.3:1) was treated with 2.4 equiv of Pb(OAc)₄ in AcOH under MW heating (90 °C for 5 min), the topologically complex polycyclic *bis*-

acetals **3a** and **4a** were formed in good yield and nearly 3.3:1 ratio.^[15] In the case of **1d**, the analogous Friedel-Crafts ring closure occurred to the extent of 50%, the minor component of the reaction crude being the path B domino product **4d** (22%). Table 2 outlines the application of the optimized reaction conditions (entries 1–8) to aromatic carbinol tethered substrate-diols **1a–h**, which were transformed to the corresponding path A and B type domino products. As further verification of a path A type reaction pathway, the behavior of substrates **1i–k** was tested under microwave assisted domino conditions with Pb(OAc)₄ as domino promoter. These substrate-diols are strongly predisposed toward an intermediate methoxymethylenefuranylium ion formation from intermediate **iii** (Scheme 1), affording **4i–k**, and no conditions could be found for making them react in the path A mode, irrespective of their C11 (*R** or *S**) configuration. It was thus shown that missing or misplaced donors on the aromatic ring, completely shut down the type A domino path, since neither substrate-diols of type **1i** nor **1j,k** undergo intramolecular cycloalkylation. The results of these evaluations are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3. All reactions on substrate diols **1** (1 equiv), in the indicated solvent (5.0 mL/mmol), were run under the following conditions. Interrupted domino process: PhI(OAc)₂ (1.1 equiv) in MeCN, at 25 °C. Full domino process: Pb(OAc)₄ (2.4 equiv) in AcOH, MW irr. 5 min at 90 °C.

In assigning the structure for these path B-type domino products two possible stereochemical orientations of the aryl group and H-11 could be conceived (e.g. structures (11*S**)-**4i** and (11*R**)-**4i**, Figure 2). The stereochemical attributions for (11*S**)/(11*R**) configurations followed directly from ¹H NMR 2D NOESY and HMBC experiments carried out on the isolated domino products. The conformational rigidity imposed on (11*S**)-**4** and (11*R**)-**4** as a consequence of the presence of the dioxane ring was of advantage to stereochemical assignment by means of NOE studies. Accordingly, the epimers were distinguished by the demonstration of diagnostic NOE's between H11 and the corresponding ring protons at C8 for (11*R**)-**4i** and H11/H1 for (11*S**)-**4i**. X-ray diffraction confirmed the NMR spectroscopic structure elucidation and established the path B domino product (11*R**)-**4d** as shown in Scheme 3, in which the aromatic ring is *anti* to the cyclohexane ring.

Figure 2. Key NOESY correlations used to establish the C11 relative configurations depicted on PM3 minimized structures (11*R*^{*})-4*i* and (11*S*^{*})-4*i*, from which the acetate substituents have been deleted to permit a clearer view.

We also studied the behavior of methoxy derivative (11*S*^{*})-1*j*, obtained epimerically pure. First, an interrupted domino experiment using $\text{PhI}(\text{OAc})_2$ was realized as mechanistic probe for distinguishing the domino pathways. This cleanly afforded (11*S*^{*})-2*j*, in 80% isolated yield thus confirming the stereochemical purity of the precursor molecule. Each one, independently, was then subjected to domino conditions with $\text{Pb}(\text{OAc})_4$ in AcOH under microwave heating (90 °C, 5 min) to afford solely the path B domino product (11*S*^{*})-4*j* in 79% yield (Scheme 4). X-ray crystallography verified the structure (11*S*^{*})-4*j* for the path B domino product, further confirming our hypothesis that the (11*S*^{*}) configuration was required to insure this domino path, provided that the arene is appropriately substituted.

Scheme 4: Complete shutdown of path A with arenes possessing donors in an inappropriate position, although (11*S*^{*}) configured.

The results are consistent with either internal π -nucleophile or heteroatom-promoted anchimerically assisted deplumbation and can be accounted for by writing a series of interconversions with the cyclization occurring through either **ii** or **iii** organolead intermediates (Scheme 1). In the (11*S*^{*}) series,

the sterically assisted C-C bonding leads to a type-3 domino product via a cycloalkylating closure, while (11*R**)-substrate diols, which contain structural features that restrict attainment of the normal transition states for path A, show a clear bias toward path B (oxidative/pericyclic/oxonium) type-4 domino products. In the carbinol-tethered series (**1a-k**), substrate-diol **1a** appears to represent the lower limit of arene reactivity required to observe cycloalkylation, since nonactivated arenes (possessing no electron-donor groups, e.g. **1i**) or those possessing them in an inappropriate position (**1j**, **1k**) failed to give path A type domino products.^[16]

Extension of the methodology to methylene-tethered domino probes

At the outset, it was anticipated that bicyclic ene-diol motif may serve as a general template for a variety of substrate-diols having each time the angular substituent replaced with another functionality.^[1-6] A limitation of this potentially powerful type A domino path was that unactivated arenes (e.g., **1i**) do not participate in the Friedel-Crafts cyclisation event. Yet another limitation was that in the presence of a methoxy substituent at the ortho position, exemplified with compounds **1j** and **1k**, the type A domino path was suppressed. Up to the present, the discussion has been centered on the type-1 carbinol-tethered octalin-diol series, where two domino paths (A and B) are put in competition with the reaction course directed towards either of two distinct pathways, simply by the appropriate choice of the C11 configuration.

Scheme 5. Pb(OAc)₄ mediated oxidative cleavage under various conditions. Path C: deplumbation *via* Friedel-Crafts cyclisation. Path D: deplumbation *via* ring-expansion.

We imagined that the methylene tethered type-1' octaline diols could also provide a path-selective synthesis of various original scaffolds. So, by removing the heteroatom at C11 we could tune the

selectivity varying the reaction parameters (temperature and solvent) and have the new domino precursors reacting through a carbon-mediated deplumbation by either path C or D. Indeed, in contrast to the domino reactions of ene-diols **1i**, the benzyl tethered diol **1'i**, first tested (along with its corresponding half-cascade **2'i**), undergoes intramolecular cyclization via path C (**5i**), but also ring-expansion via path D (**6i**), in various proportions depending on the applied domino conditions (Scheme 5). Subjecting **1'i** to oxidative cleavage with Pb(OAc)₄ in AcOH at 70 °C under microwave heating for 5 min, afforded a 1:3 mixture of domino products **5i** and **6i** respectively, in 70% overall yield (Table 4, entry 1). When higher temperatures were employed the regioselectivity improved, albeit at the expense of product yield. Thus, on treating diol **1'i** (or half-cascade **2'i**) at 90 °C for 5 min, a still better ratio favoring **6i** was observed, (**5i/6i**, 1:5) but only 30% yield was obtained, since higher temperature led to considerable decomposition (Table 4, entry 2).

Entry	Conditions	Solvent	Domino Product (overall yield %, ratio)
1	MW, 70 °C, 5 min	AcOH	5i+6i (70%, 1:3)
2	MW, 90 °C, 5 min	AcOH	5i+6i (30%, 1:5)
3	RT, 5 h	AcOH	5i+6i (68%, 1.2:1)
4	RT, 16 h	CH ₂ Cl ₂ -AcOH, 1:1	5i+6i (69%, 3:1)
5	RT, 16h	CH ₂ Cl ₂ -AcOH, 2:1	5i+6i (75%, 4:1)
6	RT, 16 h	CH ₂ Cl ₂ -AcOH, 4:1	5i+6i (68%, 5:1)

Table 4. Conditions screening in the oxidative cleavage of **1'i**. Reactions were run with Pb(OAc)₄ (2.4 equiv) in the indicated solvent (5.0 mL/mmol), under MW irr. 5 min at either 70 or 90 °C or at ambient temperature.

Challenged by the poor **5i** to **6i** ratio we have examined the process in more detail in hopes of improving the regiochemical outcome one way or another. As shown in Table 4, while in carbinol-tethered series nonactivated arenes such as **1i** do not participate in path A type cycloalkylation, in the methylene-tethered **1'** series, a suitably placed arene^[17] do initiate an effective Friedel-Crafts cyclisation via path C (**5i**), even when the arene is unactivated. Furthermore, due to the absence of heteroatom at C11, **1'i** reacts in a different manner to the bicyclic diols discussed above since path D (ring-expansion) could be observed. The *cis*-fused [6+7]bicyclic system, precursor of elaborated cycloheptanes, thus obtained allow for a stereodefined access to complex heterocyclic frameworks which can be used as building block in several synthetic endeavors.^[18] The structure of **5i** (mp 129-132 °C, *t*BuOMe), first established by extensive use of 1 and 2D NMR techniques, was further corroborated by X-ray crystallography (Scheme 6). Remarkably, the path C/D selectivity (Friedel-Crafts cycloalkylation vs ring-expansion, respectively) of this domino reaction was altered considerably when the rt mode was employed in place of microwave heating. Under these conditions the reaction course was reversed, favoring the path C domino product **5i**, which indicates that heating favors path D (**6i**). An initial search of rt conditions in AcOH (rt, 5h)

revealed moderate selectivity (**5i/6i**, 1.2:1, 68%, Table 4, entry 3) with the minor product being the ring-expanded **6i**. A third option for establishing a more C-selective path entailed the use of a mixed solvent system. Thus, reaction of substrate-diol **1'i** at rt for 16 h in 1:1 CH₂Cl₂–AcOH gave a 69% yield of **5i** and **6i** (3:1), along with recovered half-cascade intermediate **2'i** (Table 4, entry 4). Using a CH₂Cl₂–AcOH (2:1) solvent system gave 75% of **5i** and **6i** (4:1), while the best **5i/6i** ratio (5:1) was obtained using a 4:1 mixture of CH₂Cl₂–AcOH as solvent system, though in lower yield (68%, along with a considerable amount of intermediate **2'i**, Table 4, entry 5 and 6). Thus, the benzyl tethered **1'i**, participates in two competing domino paths (C and D), depending upon experimental parameters. In all room temperature runs, dominant reaction pathway after generation of the transient organolead intermediate **ii** (Scheme 5) was the cycloalkylation through **iv**, while C5-C10 bond migration leading to a ring expansion *via* **v** was less prevalent. The successful screening of the **1'i** to **5i/6i** conversion prompted a detailed analysis of the response of the substrates **1'c,d,f,i** compiled in Scheme 6, which served as templates.

Scheme 6. Complete shut down of the ring-expanding domino path (D) was realized in cases **5c,d** and **f** by using a combined solvent system such as 2:1, CH₂Cl₂–AcOH at rt. [a] A 16% of **6i** was also obtained in this case.

We first prepared the isolable and stable half-cascades **2'c,d,f,i**, obtained using PhI(OAc)₂ as the domino promoter, which were then served as the domino precursors for the Pb(OAc)₄ mediated oxidative cleavage. The optimal binary solvent medium selected for this transformation, was a 2:1 mixture of CH₂Cl₂–AcOH. The reaction was complete in 20 h at 25 °C (all starting material consumed), and no type-6 domino product (path D, ring-expanded) was observed. Whereas **1'i** underwent Friedel-Crafts cycloalkylation accompanied by ring expansion, varying the electronic content of the aromatic nucleus, as in **1'c,d,f**, afforded only **5c,d,f** (cycloalkylation).

Bringing to light new reaction pathways

An unexplored reactivity uncovered through experimentation

The selectivity trend noted during conditions screening on **1'i** strongly suggests that heat enhances the path selectivity for the ring-expanded domino product. We thus briefly explored the behavior of **1'c**, selected as an activated arene-containing representative. Whilst microwave assisted thermal reaction (70 °C, AcOH, 5 min) on **1'i** led to a mixture of Friedel-Crafts cycloalkylation (**5i**, minor) and ring expansion (**6i**, major), we found that **1'c**, under the same temperature and time frame as above led not to any of these two domino products, but to the acetoxy-butyrolactol bridged unsymmetrical octahydroanthracene ($2R^*$, S^*)-**8c** as an epimeric mixture at C2 (path E)^[19] and to a ring-contracted domino product **9c**, both never observed before (Scheme 7). The minor product in all runs was the polycyclic acetal **9c** in which a formaldehyde group, originating from C3 was lost. A 50% overall yield was obtained reproducibly, with a ($2R^*$, S^*)-**8c** (equilibrium mixture, R^*/S^* : 2:1) to **9c** ratio of 1.4 to 1. The isolable and stable **2'c** subjected to the same MW-assisted domino conditions, afforded cleanly the same product distribution in somehow higher yields (*ca.* 60%, 1.4:1 ratio). The results are consistent with a reaction mechanism which proceeds from the oxocarbenium intermediate **vi** via an ene-acetal opening yielding oxocarbenium **vii**, followed by a concomitant acetate attack ending at **8c**. We believe the minor domino product **9c** resulted through a multi-step process involving acetoxylation at C2, a ring contraction brought about by the formaldehyde loss with subsequent formation of an acetoxy-oxonium intermediate **viii**, which collapses by removal of the acetate group. A synopsis of the possible sequence of events is provided in Scheme 7.

Scheme 7. Path E: oxocarbenium formation at C2 (**vi**) and subsequent trapping with acetate (**8c**); ring contraction with loss of formaldehyde (**9c**).

Despite the fact that the data do not permit an unambiguous conclusion to be drawn about the sequence of events portrayed in Scheme 7, the simplest scenario is that acetate attack at C2 is not a concerted process (intramolecular delivery as in **ii** Scheme 5) but rather occurs intermolecularly.^[20] Yet, there is a notable exception to the above mentioned domino reactions (Scheme 1), relating to the behavior of substrate diol **1'c** (and half-cascade **2'c**) under microwave heating. While the origin of the site changing of acetate ion attack remains undefined, (*2S**)-**8c** but also (*2R**)-**8c** may well be a precursor for **9c**. This key point was experimentally clarified by subjecting the domino product (*2R**, *S**)-**8c** (C2 epimeric mixture) to Pb(OAc)₄ under MW heating as above, which cleanly afforded **9c** along with recovered (*2R**, *S**)-**8c** as an equilibrium mixture (*R*/S**, 2:1). It is worth noting that under identical conditions, epimerically pure (*2R**)-**8c** gives also **9c** along with (*2R**, *S**)-**8c** as an equilibrium mixture thus confirming also the portrayed (*2R**-*2S**)-equilibration prior to pentacycle acetoxonium **viii** formation and collapse (Scheme 7). Though the ring-contracted domino product **9c** showed a reluctance to crystallize, one of its hypothetical precursors, (*2R**)-**8c**, was isolated as a white crystalline solid, which was recrystallized from *t*BuOMe (mp 157-159 °C) and provided crystals suitable for X-ray analysis. Through our efforts it has also been possible to isolate reproducibly **9c**, and to obtain a single crystal for an X-ray crystallographic analysis thus confirming the proposed structure. The unusual pathway E could be completely switched-off by solvent and temperature control. To favor type C and prevent competing type E domino paths, a combined solvent system (CH₂Cl₂:AcOH) and rt stirring should be used, while heating in AcOH (either conventional or microwave) should be avoided. Further support for the proposed structures came from the observation that reductive treatment of the domino product (*2R**, *S**)-**8c** (C2 epimeric mixture) with TiCl₄-Et₃SiH provided an oxa-bridged unsymmetrical octahydroanthracene (*u*-8Ha, **10c**) as a single product in a reproducible 66% yield.^[21] The presence of the Lewis basic oxygen functionality in the α -oriented side chain at C4 offers opportunities to explore directed functionalization processes securing selectivity (Scheme 8).

Scheme 8. Reductive acetal cleavage as a further structural proof.

Regardless of the different mechanistic pathways by which the domino process can proceed, the outcome of this two-step protocol (ene-diol oxidation/acetal reduction) appeared ideally suited for a straightforward synthesis of the oxabridged octahydroanthracene core **10c**. In addition to the spectral and

analytical evidence that supported the assigned structure of **9c**, reliable chemical evidence was also obtained by treatment with TiCl_4 - Et_3SiH in CH_2Cl_2 . This converted **9c** into *cis* and *trans*-**11c** via reductive acetal opening (Scheme 9).

Scheme 9. The concavity of the β -face (**xi**; conformation control) regulated the sense of addition, leading to *cis/trans*-**11c** in a 3:1 ratio.

X-ray quality crystals of an aldehyde derivative (Dess-Martin periodinane, CH_2Cl_2),^[22] *trans*-**12c**, were obtained by crystallization from *t*BuOMe confirming its structure as depicted (Scheme 9). Besides providing support for the proposed structures, the latter experiments formed the basis of a two-step protocol that led to the successful acquisition of a series of novel architectures whose structures and reactions are the basis of the next article.

To conclude, running the domino reaction in anisole as solvent or in the presence of a large excess of trimethoxy benzene did not allow for intermolecular oxocarbenium trapping (Friedel-Crafts type alkylation). So far, the intramolecular cycloalkylating path seems limited to arene-containing substrates, since octalin-diols bearing an ethynyl carbinol at the angular position follow the serial B path, giving type-4 products as a mixture of diastereomers (see Supporting information).^[23]

Conclusion

By studying the domino reactions of carbinol-tethered diols **1** and benzyl-tethered diols **1'** we hoped to examine the effect of both the C11 configuration and the pendent arene substituent. This work demonstrates that electron rich aromatic rings or heteroatomic side chains are able to bridge and facilitate the collapse of an organolead (IV) intermediate, leading to complex polycyclic acetals. We showed that appropriate variation of the substitution pattern, along with judicious choice of reaction conditions, could

pave the way for the crucial demplumbation step and thus lead to completion of the skeletal reorganization towards either domino product selectively. The mechanistic rationales depicted in Schemes 1, 5 and 7 allow us to predict a whole range of modular domino transformations based on the mode of deplumbation, establishing that tether control groups at the angular position have a dramatic influence on the reaction outcome. Finally, the domino chemistry leading to topologically complex polycyclic acetals of type-3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8 and 9 from type 1/1' ene-diols offers a broad field for theoretical chemists to elucidate the results described in this paper, which derived from experimental details.

Experimental Section

General: See ref.^[8]

General procedures for Domino Reactions.

Method A: PhI(OAc)₂ mediated oxidative cleavage. A dry flask was charged with 1.0 mmol of a bicyclic unsaturated diol (diastereomeric mixture) and 1.2 mmol of PhI(OAc)₂, closed, vacuumed, flushed with argon and cooled to 0 °C. Acetonitrile (5 mL) was added, the cooling bath removed soon after and the mixture was stirred at room temperature while monitoring by TLC. After TLC analysis indicated consumption of the starting diol and conversion of the intermediate dialdehyde into the cyclic ene-acetal, the reaction mixture was diluted with *t*BuOMe (or Et₂O) and filtered through celite. The filtrate was concentrated and purified by flash chromatography (SiO₂).

Lead tetraacetate mediated oxidative cleavage.

Method B: conventional domino conditions. Placed in a flame dried flask, unsaturated diols (1.0 mmol, diastereomeric mixture) and Pb(OAc)₄ (2.4 mmol) were vacuumed, flushed with argon and cooled to 0 °C. Acetic acid (5 mL) was added, the ice bath removed soon after, and the mixture was stirred at room temperature until TLC monitoring showed no starting material left. The reaction mixture was diluted with *t*BuOMe (or Et₂O), brine was added followed by NaHCO₃, the organic layer was dried over MgSO₄ and filtered. The filtrate was concentrated and purified by flash chromatography (SiO₂).

Method C: microwaves assisted domino conditions. A microwave tube was charged with a solution of a bicyclic unsaturated diol (0.1 mmol) and Pb(OAc)₄ (0.24 mmol) in 1 mL of AcOH, sealed with a septum and inserted inside a microwave cavity. The reaction mixture was magnetically stirred for 5 min at the temperature indicated in each case. After cooling to room temperature, the crude reaction was diluted with Et₂O (or *t*BuOMe), brine was added followed by NaHCO₃, the organic layer was dried over MgSO₄, filtered, concentrated and purified by flash chromatography (SiO₂).

Method D: general procedure for domino reaction on methylene tethered series. To a flask charged with a bicyclic unsaturated diol (0.5 mmol) and Pb(OAc)₄ (1.2 mmol), vacuumed and flushed with argon, CH₂Cl₂ (1.0 mL) and AcOH (0.5 mL) were added. This mixture was stirred at room temperature until

TLC analysis indicated complete transformation of the starting material (usually 20h). The reaction mixture was then diluted with *t*BuOMe, brine was added followed by NaHCO₃, the organic layer was dried over MgSO₄, filtered, concentrated and purified by flash chromatography (SiO₂). NMR spectra for these compounds were recorded in C₆D₆ due to their instability in chloroform-*d*.

Representative Examples for Domino Transformations. Domino Reactions of Substrate-diols 1b-d.

Synthesis of (11*S)-4b.** Oxidative cleavage of **1b** (220 mg, 0.63 mmol, diastereomeric mixture, dr = 4:1), using method B over 5h, afforded after flash chromatography (SiO₂, heptane/EtOAc, 4:1) 37.2 mg (17%) of the single diastereomeric compound (11*S**)-**2b** and 147.5 mg (65%) of “Path B” domino compound (11*R**)-**4b**. Subjection of (11*S**)-**2b** (37 mg, 0.107 mmol), to conventional domino conditions using method B over 16h, afforded “Path A” domino compound **3b** (14.1 mg, 44%) and “Path B” domino compound (11*S**)-**4b** (12.7 mg, 33%). **Domino product (11*S**)-4b:** colourless oil; IR (film): ν_{max} = 2943, 1740, 1601, 1585, 1454, 1238, 1142, 1049, 939, 728 cm⁻¹; ¹H-NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃): δ = 0.53-0.61 (m, 1 H), 1.12-1.17 (m, 2 H), 1.36-1.46 (m, 2 H), 1.57-1.68 (m, 1 H), 2.13 (s, 3 H), 2.18-2.31 (m, 4 H), 3.82 (s, 3 H), 4.18 (s, 1 H), 5.31 (s, 1 H), 5.63 (d, *J* = 3.8 Hz, 1 H), 6.09 (s, 1 H), 6.80-6.83 (m, 3 H), 7.24-7.27 (m, 1 H); ¹³C-NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃): δ = 17.6, 18.5, 21.4, 29.9, 30.0, 49.9, 51.6, 55.3, 83.0, 88.0, 90.6, 91.5, 98.6, 111.9, 112.6, 118.4, 129.2, 142.1, 159.6, 170.0; ESIMS (MeOH): 383.2 ([*M* + Na]⁺, 100); HRESIMS: *m/z* calcd. for C₂₀H₂₄O₆Na: 383.1471; found: 383.1475.

Synthesis of (11*S)-4c.** Oxidative cleavage of **1c** (260 mg, 0.69 mmol, diastereomeric mixture, dr = 3.3:1), using method B over 5h, afforded after flash chromatography (SiO₂, heptane/EtOAc, 4:1) 69.8 mg (27%) of the single diastereomer (11*S**)-**2c** and 129.2 (48%) of domino compound (11*R**)-**4c**. Subjection of (11*S**)-**2c** (69 mg, 0.18 mmol) to conventional domino conditions using method B over 36h, afforded “Path A” domino compound **3c** (35.0 mg, 58%) and “Path B” domino compound (11*S**)-**4c** (3.6 mg, 5%).

Domino Product (11*S)-4c:** colourless oil; IR (film): ν_{max} = 2926, 2852, 1739, 1598, 1460, 1372, 1241, 1154, 1052, 944, 906, 727 cm⁻¹; ¹H-NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃): δ = 0.61-0.72 (m, 1 H), 1.14-1.22 (m, 3 H), 1.37-1.50 (m, 2 H), 1.58-1.71 (m, 2 H), 2.14 (s, 2 H), 2.17-2.25 (m, 2 H), 2.28 (d, *J* = 13.3 Hz, 1 H), 3.80 (s, 6 H), 4.16 (s, 1 H), 5.27 (s, 1 H), 5.63 (d, *J* = 3.8 Hz, 1 H), 6.08 (s, 1 H), 6.38 (d, *J* = 2.2 Hz, 1 H), 6.40 (d, *J* = 2.1 Hz, 2 H); ¹³C-NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃): δ = 17.6, 18.4, 29.7 (2 C), 29.8, 29.9, 50.0, 51.5, 55.4, 83.0, 88.0, 90.8, 91.5, 98.7, 99.1, 104.3 (2 C), 143.0, 160.7 (2 C), 170.0; ESIMS (CH₃CN): 454.2 ([*M* + Na + CH₃CN]⁺, 100); HRESIMS: *m/z* calcd. for C₂₃H₂₉NO₇Na: 454.1842; found: 454.1840.

Synthesis of (11*S)-4d.** Oxidative cleavage of **1d** (115 mg, 0.28 mmol, diastereomeric mixture, dr = 2.5:1), using method B over 5h, afforded after flash chromatography (SiO₂, heptane/EtOAc, 4:1) 38.9 mg (34%) of the single diastereomer (11*S**)-**2d** and 34.1 mg (29%) of “Path B” domino compound (11*R**)-**4d**. Subjection of (11*S**)-**2d** (39 mg, 0.095 mmol), to conventional domino conditions using method B over

36h, afforded “Path A” domino compound **3b** (20.9 mg, 61%) and “Path B” domino compound (11*S**)-**4d** (9.6 mg, 24%).

Domino Product (11*S)-4d:** colourless oil; IR (film): $\nu = 2938, 1741, 1591, 1416, 1331, 1233, 1125, 1008, 944, 802, 728 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (500 MHz, CDCl_3): $\delta = 0.62\text{-}0.74$ (m, 1 H), 1.15-1.24 (m, 2 H), 1.41-1.46 (m, 2 H), 1.57-1.66 (m, 2 H), 2.14 (s, 3 H), 2.19-2.24 (m, 2 H), 2.29 (d, $J = 13.4 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 3.85 (s, 3 H), 3.86 (s, 6 H), 4.17 (s, 1 H), 5.28 (s, 1 H), 5.64 (d, $J = 3.8 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 6.08 (s, 1 H), 6.46 (s, 2 DH); $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (125 MHz, CDCl_3): $\delta = 17.5, 18.3, 21.4, 29.9$ (3 C), 50.0, 51.4, 56.2 (2 C), 61.0, 83.1, 88.0, 90.9, 91.5, 98.6, 103.1 (2 C), 136.0, 153.2 (2 C), 170.0; ESIMS (MeOH): 443.2 ($[M + \text{Na}]^+$, 100); HRMS (ESI): m/z calcd. for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}_8\text{Na}$: 443.1682; found: 443.1692.

Domino Reactions in Methylene Tethered Series: Synthesis of **2'c**, **5c**, **8c** and **9c**.

Interrupted Cascade. The oxidative cleavage of **1'c** (160 mg, 0.503 mmol, diastereomeric mixture), using method A over 4h afforded after flash chromatography (SiO_2 , heptane/EtOAc, 4:1) 139.9 mg (88%) of domino product **2'c**: white solid, m.p. = 103-105 °C (*t*BuOMe); IR (film): $\nu = 2910, 1630, 1580, 1340, 1313, 1250, 1120, 900, 720 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (300 MHz, CDCl_3): $\delta = 1.20\text{-}1.28$ (m, 1 H), 1.35-1.50 (m, 3 H), 1.51-1.62 (m, 3 H), 1.79 (dd, $J = 5.7, 13.7 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 2.03 (d, $J = 11.8 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 2.36 (d, $J = 13.7 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 2.65 (d, $J = 13.3 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 2.91 (d, $J = 13.2 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 3.76 (s, 6 H), 4.86 (d, $J = 6.0 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 5.66 (d, $J = 5.5 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 6.26 (d, $J = 6.0 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 6.29-6.34 (m, 3 H); $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (75 MHz, CDCl_3): $\delta = 20.6, 21.1, 29.2, 31.1, 36.4, 48.5, 53.8, 55.1$ (2 C), 82.2, 97.7, 99.3, 108.0 (2 C), 109.9, 139.5, 141.7, 160.4 (2 C); ESIMS (MeOH): 317.2 ($[M + \text{H}]^+$, 100); HRESIMS: m/z calcd. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{25}\text{O}_4$: 317.1753; found: 317.1759.

Domino Product 5c. Applying domino conditions on **2'c** (75 mg, 0.24 mmol), using method D over 20h, afforded after flash chromatography (SiO_2 , heptane/EtOAc, 2:1) 63.0 mg of deoxygenated full cascade **5c** (71%): white solid, mp: 113-116 °C (*t*BuOMe); IR (film): $\nu = 2935, 1737, 1606, 1595, 1492, 1457, 1364, 1234, 1168, 1146, 1055, 919 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (500 MHz, C_6D_6): $\delta = 0.98$ (q, $J = 13.9 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 1.13-1.24 (m, 3 H), 1.27-1.36 (m, 2 H), 1.59-1.66 (m, 1 H), 1.71 (dd, $J = 5.5, 13.7 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 1.81 (s, 3 H), 1.94 (d, $J = 13.8 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 2.07 (d, $J = 14.2 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 2.55 (d, $J = 17.8 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 2.69 (d, $J = 17.8 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 3.29 (s, 3 H), 3.43 (s, 3 H), 3.56 (d, $J = 2.7 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 5.51 (d, $J = 5.5 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 6.19 (d, $J = 2.2 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 6.25 (d, $J = 2.4 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 6.59 (d, $J = 3.2 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H); $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (125 MHz, C_6D_6): $\delta = 18.2, 18.4, 19.2, 30.3, 33.4, 35.4, 36.9, 42.8, 47.2, 51.8, 52.0, 77.6, 90.0, 94.1, 94.7, 101.8, 113.7, 133.8, 156.2, 157.2, 166.2$; ESIMS (MeOH): 315.2 ($[M - \text{OAc}]^+$, 100), 397.2 ($[M + \text{Na}]^+$, 40); HRESIMS: m/z calcd. for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_6\text{Na}$: 397.1627; found: 397.1637.

Domino Products (2*R)-8c and 9c.** Domino reaction over **2'c** (40 mg, 0.13 mmol) following method C – microwaves heating at 70 °C – gave after flash chromatography (SiO_2 , heptane/EtOAc, 4:1) a diastereomeric mixture (*R**/*S**, 2:1) of aldehyde **8c** (16.6 mg, 35%) and the pentacyclic acetal **9c** (9.6 mg,

25%). For **8c**, the major diastereomer was isolated and characterized. (*2R**)-**8c**: colourless crystals, m.p. = 157-159 °C (heptane); IR (film): ν = 2925, 2853, 1725, 1608, 1598, 1495, 1462, 1233, 1150, 1118, 982 cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (500 MHz, CDCl_3): δ = 1.19-1.27 (m, 2 H), 1.47-1.51 (m, 2 H), 1.74 (d, J = 14.3 Hz, 1 H), 1.93 (td, J = 4.0, 14.3 Hz, 1 H), 2.07 (s, 3 H), 2.08-2.11 (m, 1 H), 2.21 (dt, J = 3.1, 13.6 Hz, 1 H), 2.29-2.37 (m, 2 H), 2.92 (d, J = 15.4 Hz, 1 H), 3.72-3.75 (m, 4 H), 3.80 (s, 3 H), 3.78-3.84 (m, 1 H), 6.29 (d, J = 2.6 Hz, 1 H), 6.33 (d, J = 2.6 Hz, 1 H), 6.37 (dd, J = 5.3, 6.6 Hz, 1 H), 9.34 (d, J = 3.2 Hz, 1 H); $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (125 MHz, CDCl_3): δ = 20.7, 21.5, 22.8, 29.7, 35.2, 40.7, 41.4, 44.7, 51.7, 55.3, 55.4, 85.6, 96.5, 97.6, 104.8, 111.0, 137.6, 158.4, 160.0, 170.3, 199.3; ESIMS (MeOH): 315.2 ($[M - \text{AcO}]^+$, 100); HRESIMS: m/z calcd. for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_6\text{Na}$: 397.1627; found: 397.1619.

Domino Product 9c: crystals, m.p. = 156-158 °C (*t*BuOMe); IR (film): ν = 2931, 2855, 1605, 1458, 1210, 1149, 1087, 1034, 944, 862 cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (500 MHz, CDCl_3): δ = 1.46-1.50 (m, 2 H), 1.57-1.63 (m, 2 H), 1.69-1.71 (m, 3 H), 1.72-1.75 (m, 2 H), 2.02 (d, J = 14.1 Hz, 1 H), 2.75 (d, J = 17.8 Hz, 1 H), 3.11 (d, J = 17.8 Hz, 1 H), 3.79 (s, 3 H), 3.83 (s, 3 H), 4.60 (s, 1 H), 5.50 (s, 1 H), 6.26 (s, 1 H), 6.33 (s, 1 H); $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (125 MHz, CDCl_3): δ = 21.8, 21.9, 24.9, 34.2, 37.0, 37.7, 48.1, 55.3, 55.5, 72.5, 83.6, 96.5, 100.0, 104.2, 115.7, 136.3, 160.2, 160.8; ESIMS (MeOH): 325.2 ($[M + \text{Na}]^+$, 100); HRESIMS: m/z calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_4\text{Na}$: 325.1416; found: 325.1426.

Reductive Acetal Cleavage: General Procedure. To a solution of the corresponding acetal (0.1 mmol) in dry CH_2Cl_2 (50 mM), under argon and cooled to -78 °C, were added Et_3SiH (0.4 mmol) and TiCl_4 (0.1 mmol). After stirring at the same temperature for 10 minutes, the reaction was warmed to 0 °C and stirred for additional 30 minutes. The resulting mixture was then diluted with *t*BuOMe, worked up as usual and purified by flash chromatography (SiO_2).

Reductive cleavage of acetalic compound **8c** (15 mg, 0.040 mmol) using the general procedure afforded after flash chromatography (SiO_2 , heptane/EtOAc, 2:1) compound **10c** (8.4 mg, 66%). **10c**: white solid, m.p. = 102-104 °C (*t*BuOMe); IR (film): ν = 3526, 2926, 1608, 1464, 1202, 1148, 1119, 1025, 925, 828 cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (500 MHz, CDCl_3): δ = 1.05-1.11 (m, 2 H), 1.35-1.39 (m, 2 H), 1.42 (d, J = 14.3 Hz, 2 H), 1.57-1.64 (m, 3 H), 1.76 (dt, J = 3.0, 11.9 Hz, 1 H), 2.07 (d, J = 14.8 Hz, 1 H), 2.34-2.41 (m, 1 H), 2.93 (d, J = 14.7 Hz, 1 H), 3.38 (dd, J = 3.5, 8.0 Hz, 1 H), 3.73 (dd, J = 8.0, 10.7 Hz, 1 H), 3.78 (s, 3 H), 3.80 (s, 3 H), 3.85 (dd, J = 3.5, 10.7 Hz, 1 H), 3.96-4.05 (m, 2 H), 6.23 (d, J = 2.5 Hz, 1 H), 6.32 (d, J = 2.5 Hz, 1 H); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (125 MHz, CDCl_3): δ = 20.8, 22.3, 29.7, 34.7, 35.4, 40.4, 42.9, 44.8, 55.2 (2 C), 63.1, 64.1, 84.5, 96.4, 105.0, 116.3, 139.3, 157.6, 158.8; ESIMS (MeOH): 301.2 ($[M - \text{OH}]^+$, 100), 341.2 ($[M + \text{Na}]^+$, 50); HRESIMS: m/z calcd. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_4\text{Na}$: 341.1729; found: 341.1722.

Reductive opening of acetalic compound **9c** (20 mg, 0.066 mmol) using the general procedure afforded compound **11c** as a diastereomeric mixture (12.4 mg, 65%). After acetylation (92%), both diastereomers were separated by preparative HPLC, thus obtaining 9.6 mg of *cis*-**11c-Ac** and 3.2 mg of *trans*-**11c-Ac**

(3:1 ratio). **cis-11c-Ac**: colourless oil; IR (film): $\nu = 2919, 2850, 1736, 1595, 1463, 1232, 1206, 1145, 1052, 824 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (500 MHz, CDCl_3): $\delta = 1.25\text{-}1.33$ (m, 3 H), $1.36\text{-}1.41$ (m, 2 H), $1.50\text{-}1.56$ (m, 2 H), $1.62\text{-}1.68$ (m, 5 H), 1.99 (s, 3 H), 2.21 (d, $J = 17.0$ Hz, 1 H), 2.42 (d, $J = 18.0$ Hz, 1 H), 2.72 (dd, $J = 6.4, 18.0$ Hz, 1 H), 3.77 (s, 3 H), 3.78 (s, 3 H), $4.09\text{-}4.21$ (m, 2 H), 6.20 (d, $J = 1.8$ Hz, 1 H), 6.27 (d, $J = 1.8$ Hz, 1 H); $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (125 MHz, CDCl_3): $\delta = 21.1, 21.7, 25.9, 26.7, 29.1, 29.7, 33.7, 34.2, 34.8, 37.1, 38.0, 55.1, 55.2, 61.1, 95.8, 104.5, 115.5, 136.2, 158.3, 171.2$; ESIMS (MeOH): 333.2 ($[M + H]^+$, 100); HRESIMS : m/z calcd. for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{29}\text{O}_4$: 333.2066; found: 333.2056.

trans-11c-Ac: colourless oil; IR (film): $\nu = 2922, 2852, 1738, 1594, 1454, 1365, 1235, 1145, 1051, 825, 732 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (500 MHz, CDCl_3): $\delta = 1.05$ (td, $J = 3.1, 13.3$ Hz, 2 H), $1.22\text{-}1.36$ (m, 3 H+ HDO), $1.40\text{-}1.65$ (m, 3 H), $1.78\text{-}1.87$ (m, 3 H), 1.97 (s, 3 H), $2.03\text{-}2.09$ (m, 1 H), 2.39 (d, $J = 16.7$ Hz, 1 H), $2.59\text{-}2.66$ (m, 2 H), 3.77 (s, 3 H), 3.78 (s, 3 H), 3.97 (ddd, $J = 6.0, 9.3, 10.7$ Hz, 1 H), 4.17 (ddd, $J = 6.0, 9.3, 10.7$ Hz, 1 H), 6.18 (d, $J = 2.1$ Hz, 1 H), 6.28 (d, $J = 2.1$ Hz, 1 H); $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (125 MHz, CDCl_3): $\delta = 21.0, 21.9, 23.9, 26.4, 27.0, 28.4, 34.0, 36.3, 42.0, 43.0, 55.2, 55.3, 61.6, 95.8, 104.6, 117.1, 137.3, 157.9, 158.5, 171.2$; ESIMS (MeOH): 333.2 ($[M + H]^+$, 100); HRESIMS : m/z calcd. for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{29}\text{O}_4$: 333.2066; found: 333.2066.

Oxidation of (cis/trans)-11c. Synthesis of Aldehydes (cis/trans)-12c. Compound **11c** (18 mg, 0.062 mmol) was oxidated by adding DMP (0.150 mmol, 63.1 mg, 2.4 equiv) and pyridine (0.186 mmol, 14.7 mg, $15\mu\text{L}$, 3.0 equiv) in CH_2Cl_2 at 0°C . The reaction was then allowed to warm to room temperature and stirred for 2h. Usual workup and flash chromatography afforded **12c** (17.3 mg, 84%) in a 3 to 1 *cis/trans* ratio. Both diastereomers were separated by preparative HPLC, thus obtaining 13.0 mg of *cis-12c* and 4.3 mg of *trans-12c*.

cis-12c: colourless oil; IR (film): $\nu = 2923, 2852, 1716, 1608, 1596, 1492, 1464, 1210, 1147, 1092, 1053, 826 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (500 MHz, CDCl_3): $\delta = 1.30\text{-}1.36$ (m, 2 H), $1.42\text{-}1.48$ (m, 1 H), $1.53\text{-}1.62$ (m, 3 H), $1.67\text{-}1.74$ (m, 2 H), $1.75\text{-}1.81$ (m, 1 H), $2.29\text{-}2.40$ (m, 3 H), 2.49 (d, $J = 18.0$ Hz, 1 H), 2.73 (dd, $J = 6.7, 18.0$ Hz, 1 H), 3.19 (d, $J = 17.2$ Hz, 1 H), 3.78 (s, 3 H), 3.79 (s, 3 H), 6.22 (d, $J = 2.5$ Hz, 1 H), 6.29 (d, $J = 2.5$ Hz, 1 H), 9.89 (t, $J = 3.1$ Hz, 1 H); $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (125 MHz, CDCl_3): $\delta = 21.5$ (2 C), $25.8, 26.6, 28.9, 33.8, 35.8, 38.3, 52.5, 55.2$ (2 C), $96.1, 104.4, 115.1, 135.5, 158.5$ (2 C), 203.6 ; ESIMS (MeOH): 289.2 ($[M + \text{Na}]^+$, 100); HRESIMS: m/z calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{25}\text{O}_3$: 289.1804; found: 289.1794.

trans-12c: colourless oil; IR (film): $\nu = 2923, 2852, 1718, 1608, 1595, 1492, 1454, 1199, 1147, 1100, 1076, 1052, 826 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (500 MHz, CDCl_3): $\delta = 1.17\text{-}1.32$ (m, 2 H), 1.36 (qt, $J = 3.9, 12.8$ Hz, 1 H), $1.48\text{-}1.65$ (m, 4 H), 1.82 (d, $J = 12.4$ Hz, 1 H), $1.92\text{-}2.05$ (m, 2 H), 2.22 (dt, $J = 1.9, 14.6$ Hz, 1 H), 2.52 (ddd, $J = 1.9, 3.7, 14.6$ Hz, 1 H), 2.57 (d, $J = 17.8$ Hz, 1 H), 2.66 (dd, $J = 5.6, 17.8$ Hz, 1 H), 2.90 (d, $J = 17.2$ Hz, 1 H), 3.78 (s, 3 H), 3.79 (s, 3 H), 6.21 (d, $J = 2.5$ Hz, 1 H), 6.29 (d, $J = 2.5$ Hz, 1 H), 9.02 (dd, $J = 2.2, 3.9$ Hz, 1 H); $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (125 MHz, CDCl_3): $\delta = 21.6, 26.2, 27.1, 28.5, 29.7, 37.0, 40.6, 41.6, 43.3,$

55.2, 55.3, 96.1, 104.5, 116.7, 136.6, 158.0, 158.7, 203.8; ESIMS (MeOH): 289.2 ($[M + Na]^+$, 100); HRESIMS: m/z calcd. for $C_{18}H_{25}O_3$: 289.1804; found: 289.1797.

Supporting Information (see footnote on the first page of this article): Experimental procedures for the reactions described herein and characterization data for all new compounds.

Acknowledgments

Financial support from Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique (CNRS) and fellowship awards from Institut de Chimie des Substances Naturelles (ICSN) are gratefully acknowledged. We thank Dr Imad Safir and Dr Zobida Elkhayat for their participation in the early stages of this work and Susana Ramos for performing HPLC separations.

-
- [1] a) L. Finet, J. I. Candela Lena, T. Kaoudi, N. Birlirakis, S. Arseniyadis, *Chem. –Eur. J.* **2003**, *9*, 3813–3820; b) I. Safir, I. Castellote, S. Porcel, T. Kaoudi, N. Birlirakis, L. Toupet, S. Arseniyadis, *Chem. –Eur. J.* **2006**, *12*, 7337–7344.
- [2] a) C. Unaleroglu, V. Aviyente, S. Arseniyadis, *J. Org. Chem.* **2002**, *70*, 2447–2452; b) Z. Elkhayat, I. Safir, M. Aquino, M. Perez, Z. Gandara, P. Retailleau, S. Arseniyadis, *Eur. J. Org. Chem.* **2009**, 2687–2694.
- [3] Z. Elkhayat, I. Safir, P. Retailleau, S. Arseniyadis, *Org. Lett.* **2007**, *9*, 4841–4844.
- [4] Z. Elkhayat, I. Safir, I. Castellote, P. Retailleau, S. Arseniyadis, *Org. Lett.* **2008**, *10*, 2219–2222.
- [5] M. Aquino, I. Safir, Z. Elkhayat, Z. Gandara, M. Perez, P. Retailleau, S. Arseniyadis, *Org. Lett.* **2009**, *11*, 3610–3613.
- [6] a) A. Chanu, I. Safir, R. Basak, A. Chiaroni, S. Arseniyadis, *Org. Lett.* **2007**, *9*, 1351–1354; b) Z. Elkhayat, I. Safir, Z. Gandara, P. Retailleau, S. Arseniyadis, *Eur. J. Org. Chem.* **2010**, 4851–4860.
- [7] a) L. F. Tietze, U. Beifuss, *Angew. Chem.* **1993**, *32*, 115–136; b) L. F. Tietze, *Chem. Rev.* **1996**, *96*, 115–136; c) *Domino Reactions In Organic Synthesis* (Eds.: L. F. Tietze, G. Brasche, K. M. Gericke), Wiley-VCH, Weinheim, Germany, **2006**; d) L. F. Tietze, F. Hünert, in *Stimulating Concepts in Chemistry* (Eds.: F. Vögtle, J. F. Stoddart, M. Shibasaki), Wiley-VCH, Weinheim, Germany, **2000**, 39–64.
- [8] R. R. Castillo, M. Aquino, Z. Gandara, I. Safir, Z. Elkhayat, P. Retailleau, S. Arseniyadis, *Org. Lett.* **2012**, *14*, 1628–1631.
- [9] a) As stated by Mark Moloney, “lead(IV) has been significantly under-utilized in synthesis and further novel applications are likely to emerge, by making use of our developing understanding of the principles governing these unusual reactions.” M. G. Moloney, *Main Group Metal Chem.* **2001**, *24*, 653–660 and references cited therein. For articles dealing with specific aspects of organolead chemistry see: b) R. Criegee, in *Oxidation In Organic Chemistry* (Ed.: K. B. Wiberg), Academic Press, New York, **1965**, Part A, 277–366; c) G. M. Rubottom, in *Oxidation In Organic Chemistry* (Ed.: W. H. Trahanovsky), Academic Press, London, **1982**, Vol. D, Chapter 1.
- [10] All reactions were performed on racemic series; only one antipode is represented. The diol stereochemistry had no effect on the reaction as demonstrated by control experiments where substrates with *cis* diols performed identically to substrates with *trans* diols.

- [11] Tris-TMS (C2,3,11) or C11Bn-protected type-1 substrate diols can also be used as domino probes. In fact, it was anticipated that MOM protection of the C11 oxygen functionality in **1** would be most desirable in that deprotection would occur in the course of oxonium collapse during the deplumbation process.
- [12] For reviews on the use of microwaves in organic synthesis see: a) A. de la Hoz, A. Diaz-Ortiz, A. Moreno, F. Langa, *Eur. J. Org. Chem.* **2000**, 3659–3673; b) *Microwaves in Organic and Medicinal Chemistry* (Eds.: C. O. Kappe, A. Stadler), Wiley-VCH, Weinheim, Germany **2005**; c) C. O. Kappe, D. Dallinger, *Drug Discovery* **2006**, 5, 51–63.
- [13] For a recent review on hypervalent iodine chemistry see: V. V. Zhdankin, P. J. Stang, *Chem. Rev.* **2008**, 108, 5299–5358.
- [14] Preliminary communication.^[8] Usually, optimum yields for our domino reactions under microwave heating are obtained with the use of temperatures in the 60 °C to 90 °C range. Yields refer to average isolated yields of three separate experiments.
- [15] The ratio of half-cascade products **2a–h**, systematically measured by ¹H NMR integration of the crude reaction mixtures, can be used to predict the trends, since an inspection of this data shows that the quantitative agreement to estimate the product distribution is good.
- [16] The preparation of substrates carrying an electron-withdrawing group on the arene moiety, to divert the reaction away from the serial A pathway appeared worthless, since the Friedel-Crafts type cycloalkylation was already completely shut down by removing substituents on the aryl ring (**1i**, Table 3, entry 1).
- [17] The product distribution can be altered through the magnitude of the connecting chain.^[2b]
- [18] For routes to gain synthetic entry into cycloheptanes as synthetic goal compounds, see: a) P. A. Wender, F. C. Bi, M. A. Brodney, F. Gosselin, *Org. Lett.* **2001**, 3, 2105–2108; b) P. A. Wender, A. J. Dyckman, C. O. Husfeld, M. J. C. Scanio, *Org. Lett.* **2000**, 2, 1609–1611; c) P. A. Wender, M. Fuji, C. O. Husfeld, J. A. Love, *Org. Lett.* **1999**, 1, 137–139; d) P. A. Wender, C. O. Husfeld, E. Langkopf, J. A. Love, N. Pleuss, *Tetrahedron* **1998**, 54, 7203–7220; e) P. A. Wender, H. Rieck, M. Fuji, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **1998**, 120, 10976–10977; f) Y. Coquerel, M. H. Filippini, D. Bensa, J. Rodriguez, *Chem.–Eur. J.* **2008**, 14, 3078–3092 and references cited therein; g) B. L. Ashfeld, K. A. Miller, A. J. Smith, K. Tran, S. F. Martin, *J. Org. Chem.* **2007**, 72, 9018–9031.
- [19] Numbering is arbitrary, based mainly on steroid numbering (C1 to C10), since this is the easiest to follow. Shifting at this stage to the IUPAC anthracene numbering would have been extremely confusing.
- [20] C. Öztürk, K. Topal, V. Aviyente, N. Ş. Tüzün, E. Sánchez Fernández, S. Arseniyadis, *J. Org. Chem.* **2005**, 70, 7080–7086. Be it a concerted or stepwise process, the mixed stereochemical outcome (*2R**, *S**)-**8c** could be rationalized on the basis of steric factors.
- [21] The formation of a single diastereomer **10c** validated the inference that acetate attack at C2 from both the α and β -faces was accountable for the formation of domino products (*2R**)-**8c** and (*2S**)-**8c** respectively.
- [22] To assign the stereochemical nature of *cis* and *trans*-**11c**, transformation products via standard acetylation [*cis* and *trans*-**11c**(OAc)] and Dess-Martin oxidation (*cis* and *trans*-**12c**) were also prepared and their structures characterized (see Supporting information).
- [23] No domino product involving Prins-type carbocyclization on intermediate oxocarbenium ions could

Modular Construction of Topologically Complex Polycyclic Acetals by Tether-Controlled Domino Reactions

Rafael R. Castillo, Valentina Abet, Maurizio Aquino, Zoila Gandara, Pascal Retailleau and
Siméon Arseniyadis*

*Centre de Recherche de Gif, Institut de Chimie des Substances Naturelles, CNRS, F-91198
Gif-sur-Yvette Cedex (France)*

simeon.arseniyadis@icsn.cnrs-gif.fr

Supporting Information

Table of Contents

Section A: Experimental Procedures

S4	1. General Experimental Procedures.
S7	2. Preparation and domino reactions of substrate-diol 1i . 2.1. Preparation of substrate diol 1i .
S8	2.2. Domino reactions. Synthesis of 2i and 4i .
S10	3. Preparation and domino reactions of substrate-diol 1j . 3.1. Preparation of substrate diol 1j .
S11	3.2. Domino reactions. Synthesis of 2j and 4j .
S13	4. Preparation and domino reactions of substrate-diol 1k . 4.1. Preparation of substrate diol 1k .
	4.2. Domino reactions. Synthesis of 2k and 4k .
S15	5. Preparation and domino reactions of substrate-diol 1l . 5.1. Preparation of substrate diol 1l .
	5.2. Domino reactions. Synthesis of 2l and 4l .
S17	6. Domino reactions of substrate-diol 1b . Synthesis of (11 <i>S</i> [*])- 4b .
S18	7. Domino reactions of substrate-diol 1c . Synthesis of (11 <i>S</i> [*])- 4c .
S19	8. Domino reactions of substrate-diol 1d . Synthesis of (11 <i>S</i> [*])- 4d .
S20	9. Preparation and domino reactions of substrate-diol 1'c . 9.1. Preparation of substrate diol 1'c .
S22	9.2. Domino reactions. Synthesis of 2'c , 5c , 8c and 9c .
S24	9.3. Reductive acetal cleavage of domino products 8c and 9c . Synthesis of 10c and 11c .
S26	9.4. Oxidation of compounds 11c . Synthesis of aldehydes 12c .
S27	10. Preparation and domino reactions of substrate-diol 1'd .

- 10.1. Preparation of substrate diol **1'd**.
S28 10.2. Domino reactions. Synthesis of **2'd** and **5d**.
S29 11. Preparation and domino reactions of substrate-diol **1'f**.
11.1. Preparation of substrate diol **1'f**.
S30 11.2. Domino reactions. Synthesis of **2'f** and **5f**.
S31 12. Preparation and domino reactions of substrate-diol **1'i**.
12.1. Preparation of substrate-diol **1'i**.
S32 12.2. Domino reactions. Synthesis of **2'i**, **5i** and **6i**.
S35 13. X-ray structures for reported compounds.
S36 14. Crystallographic data for reported compounds.

Section B: NMR Spectra

- S38 ¹H-, ¹³C- and DEPT, COSY, HSQC and HMBC NMR spectra (500/125 MHz) in CDCl₃ of (11*R**)-**1i**.
S43 ¹H-, ¹³C- and DEPT NMR spectra (500/125 MHz) in CDCl₃ of **1'c-TBS**.
S45 ¹H-, ¹³C- and DEPT NMR spectra (300/75 MHz) in CDCl₃ of **1'c**.
S47 ¹H-, ¹³C- and DEPT NMR spectra (300/75 MHz) in CDCl₃ of **1'd**.
S49 ¹H-, ¹³C- and DEPT NMR spectra (300/75 MHz) in CDCl₃ of (11*S**)-**2b**.
S51 ¹H-, ¹³C- and DEPT, COSY, HSQC and HMBC NMR spectra (500/125 MHz) in CDCl₃ of (11*R**)-**2i**.
S56 ¹H-, ¹³C- and DEPT, COSY, HSQC and HMBC NMR spectra (500/125 MHz) in CDCl₃ of (11*S**)-**2i**.
S61 ¹H-, ¹³C- and DEPT NMR spectra (500/125 MHz) in CDCl₃ of **2j**.
S63 ¹H-, ¹³C- and DEPT spectra (500/125 MHz) in CDCl₃ of **2k**.
S65 ¹H-, ¹³C- and DEPT NMR spectra (500/75 MHz) in CDCl₃ of **2l**.
S67 ¹H-, ¹³C- and DEPT NMR spectra (300/75 MHz) in CDCl₃ of **2'c**.
S69 ¹H-, ¹³C- and DEPT NMR spectra (500/75 MHz) in CDCl₃ of **2'd**.
S71 ¹H-, ¹³C- and DEPT NMR spectra (300/75 MHz) in CDCl₃ of **2'f**.
S73 ¹H-, ¹³C- and DEPT, COSY, HSQC and HMBC NMR spectra (300/75 MHz) in CDCl₃ of **2'i**.
S78 ¹H-, ¹³C- and DEPT NMR spectra (500/125 MHz) in CDCl₃ of (11*S**)-**4b**.
S80 ¹H-, ¹³C- and DEPT NMR spectra (500/125 MHz) in CDCl₃ of (11*S**)-**4c**.
S82 ¹H-, ¹³C- and DEPT NMR spectra (500/125 MHz) in CDCl₃ of (11*S**)-**4d**.
S84 ¹H-, ¹³C- and DEPT, COSY, HSQC and HMBC NMR spectra (500/125 MHz) in CDCl₃ of (11*R**)-**4i**.
S89 ¹H-, ¹³C- and DEPT, COSY, HSQC and HMBC NMR spectra (500/125 MHz) in CDCl₃ of (11*S**)-**4i**.
S94 ¹H-, ¹³C- and DEPT NMR spectra (500/125 MHz) in CDCl₃ of **4j**.
S96 ¹H-, ¹³C- and DEPT NMR spectra (500/125 MHz) in C₆D₆ of **5c**.

- S98 ^1H -, ^{13}C - and DEPT NMR spectra (500/125 MHz) in C_6D_6 of **5d**.
- S100 ^1H -, ^{13}C - and DEPT NMR spectra (500/75 MHz) in C_6D_6 of **5f**.
- S102 ^1H -, ^{13}C - and DEPT, COSY, HSQC, HMBC and NOESY NMR spectra (500/125 MHz) in CDCl_3 of **5i**.
- S108 ^1H -, ^{13}C - and DEPT, COSY, HSQC and HMBC NMR spectra (500/75 MHz) in CDCl_3 of **6i**.
- S113 ^1H -, ^{13}C - and DEPT, COSY, HSQC and HMBC NMR spectra (500/125 MHz) in CDCl_3 of **8c**.
- S118 ^1H -, ^{13}C - and DEPT, COSY, HSQC, HMBC and NOESY NMR spectra (500/125 MHz) in C_6D_6 of **9c**.
- S124 ^1H -, ^{13}C - and DEPT, COSY, HSQC and HMBC NMR spectra (500/125 MHz) in CDCl_3 of **10c**.
- S129 ^1H -, ^{13}C - and DEPT, COSY, HSQC and HMBC NMR spectra (500/125 MHz) in CDCl_3 of *cis*-**11c-Ac**.
- S134 ^1H -, ^{13}C - and DEPT, COSY, HSQC and HMBC NMR spectra (500/125 MHz) in CDCl_3 of *trans*-**11c-Ac**.
- S139 ^1H -, ^{13}C - and DEPT, COSY, HSQC, HMBC and NOESY NMR spectra (500/125 MHz) in CDCl_3 of *cis*-**12c**.
- S145 ^1H -, ^{13}C - and DEPT, COSY, HSQC, HMBC and NOESY NMR spectra (500/125 MHz) in CDCl_3 of *trans*-**12c**.

SECTION A: EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

1. General Experimental Procedures

"Usual work up" means washing of the organic layer with brine, drying on anhydrous MgSO₄, and evaporating in vacuo with a rotary evaporator at aspirator pressure. Melting points (uncorrected) were determined with the aid of a Büchi B-540 apparatus; IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin–Elmer Spectrum BX instrument with an FT-IR system; IR bands absorptions are given in cm⁻¹. NMR spectra were run in CDCl₃ or C₆D₆ at 25°C unless otherwise noted. Experimental evidence favoring the structures investigated came from a comprehensive range of ¹H- and ¹³C-NMR data (500/125 and 300/75 MHz respectively, 1D and 2D experiments) and corroborated by spatial proximity (NOE) studies using the 2D NOESY technique. For all compounds investigated, multiplicities of ¹³C resonances were assigned by the DEPT technique. ¹H chemical shifts are expressed in ppm downfield from TMS using the residual non deuterated solvent as internal standard (CDCl₃ ¹H, 7.26 ppm; C₆D₆ ¹H, 7.15 ppm). ¹³C chemical shifts are reported relative to CDCl₃ and C₆D₆ triplets centered at 77.0 and 128.0 ppm respectively. Mass spectra acquired in the positive ion mode under electron spray ionization (ES⁺) using a mobile phase of methanol will be abbreviated as ESIMS. HR will be added for the high-resolution mass measurements – HRESIMS–.

The required unsaturated diols were prepared straightforwardly following published procedures. Pb(OAc)₄ was purchased from Aldrich Chemicals and used as received. The acetic acid content of the latter (introduced in excess of 0.2 equiv) was mostly removed under vacuum in the reaction vessel. Given the fact that Pb(OAc)₄ mediated domino transformations are insensitive to diol stereochemistry, the starting diols were used as diastereomeric mixtures. However, for certain examples, were separated *cis* or *trans* diols for characterization purposes.

The following five crystal structures have been deposited at the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre and allocated the deposition numbers CCDC **4j** (903924), **5i** (903925), **8c** (903926), **9c** (903927) and *trans*-**12c** (903928). Copies of the data can be obtained free of charge on application to CCDC, 12 Union Road, Cambridge CB21EZ, UK (fax: (+44)1223-336-033; e-mail: deposit@ccdc.cam.ac.uk).

1.1. General procedure for MOM protection.

To an ice-cold solution of alcohol (1.0 mmol) in 10 mL of dry CH_2Cl_2 under argon, diisopropylethylamine (4.2 mmol) and chloromethyl methylether (4 mmol) were added. The reaction mixture was then allowed to warm and stirred to room temperature until complete protection. The resulting mixture was then quenched with water, the aqueous solution was extracted with CH_2Cl_2 , the combined organic layers were washed with diluted HCl and saturated aq. solution of NaHCO_3 . Workup as usual and flash chromatography (SiO_2) afforded the desired protected alcohol.

1.2 General procedure for xanthate formation.

To a solution of alcohol (1.0 mmol) in 10 mL of dry THF under argon and cooled to $-78\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, NaHMDS 1.0 M in THF (3.0 mmol) was added, followed, after 30 min, by carbon disulfide (6.0 mmol). The reaction was then allowed to warm to $-50\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and stirred for 1h. Finally, it was cooled to $-78\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and MeI (3.2 mmol) was added. The cooling bath was removed and the stirring maintained for an additional hour. The mixture was diluted with *t*BuOMe, washed with saturated aq. $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ solution, worked up as usual and purified by flash chromatography (SiO_2).

1.3 General procedure for deoxygenation.

A solution of the previous xanthate (1.0 mmol), AIBN (10 mol%) and Bu_3SnH (4.0 mmol) in well deoxygenated toluene (75 mL) under argon was stirred at $110\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 2h. After complete conversion, the solvent was removed in vacuo and the crude mixture was purified by flash chromatography (SiO_2).

1.4. General procedure for fluoride deprotection.

To a stirred solution of TBS-protected alcohol (1.0 mmol), tetrabutylammonium fluoride (4.0 mmol) was added. The reaction was warmed to $60\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and stirred until TLC monitoring showed no starting material left (usually 4h). After dilution with EtOAc, workup as usual and flash chromatography (SiO_2) afforded the expected diol.

1.5. General procedure for Domino Reactions.

1.5.1. Interrupted (half-cascade) domino process.

Method A: $\text{PhI}(\text{OAc})_2$ mediated oxidative cleavage. A dry flask was charged with 1.0 mmol of a bicyclic unsaturated diol (diastereomeric mixture) and 1.2 mmol of $\text{PhI}(\text{OAc})_2$, closed, vacuumed, flushed with argon and cooled to $0\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Acetonitrile (5 mL) was added, the cooling bath removed soon after and the mixture was stirred at room temperature while monitoring by TLC. After TLC analysis indicated consumption of the starting diol and conversion of the intermediate dialdehyde into the cyclic ene-acetal,

the reaction mixture was diluted with *t*BuOMe (or Et₂O) and filtered through celite. The filtrate was concentrated and purified by flash chromatography (SiO₂).

1.5.2. Lead tetraacetate mediated oxidative cleavage in AcOH.

Method B: conventional domino conditions. Placed in a flame dried flask, unsaturated diols (1.0 mmol, diastereomeric mixture) and Pb(OAc)₄ (2.4 mmol) were vacuumed, flushed with argon and cooled to 0 °C. Acetic acid (5 mL) was added, the ice bath removed soon after, and the mixture was stirred at room temperature until TLC monitoring showed no starting material left. The reaction mixture was diluted with *t*BuOMe (or Et₂O), brine was added followed by NaHCO₃, the organic layer was dried over MgSO₄ and filtered. The filtrate was concentrated and purified by flash chromatography (SiO₂).

Method C: microwaves assisted domino conditions. A microwave tube was charged with a solution of a bicyclic unsaturated diol (0.1 mmol) and Pb(OAc)₄ (0.24 mmol) in 1 mL of AcOH, sealed with a septum and inserted inside a microwave cavity. The reaction mixture was magnetically stirred for 5 min at the temperature indicated in each case. After cooling to room temperature, the crude reaction was diluted with Et₂O (or *t*BuOMe), brine was added followed by NaHCO₃, the organic layer was dried over MgSO₄, filtered, concentrated and purified by flash chromatography (SiO₂).

Method D: general procedure for domino reaction on methylene tethered series. To a flask charged with a bicyclic unsaturated diol (0.5 mmol) and Pb(OAc)₄ (1.2 mmol), vacuumed and flushed with argon, CH₂Cl₂ (1.0 mL) and AcOH (0.5 mL) were added. This mixture was stirred at room temperature until TLC analysis indicated complete transformation of the starting material (usually 20h). The reaction mixture was then diluted with *t*BuOMe, brine was added followed by NaHCO₃, the organic layer was dried over MgSO₄, filtered, concentrated and purified by flash chromatography (SiO₂). NMR spectra for these compounds were recorded in C₆D₆ due to their instability in chloroform-*d*.

1.6. Reductive acetal cleavage.

To a solution of the corresponding acetal (0.1 mmol) in dry CH₂Cl₂ (50 mM), under argon and cooled to -78 °C, were added Et₃SiH (0.4 mmol) and TiCl₄ (0.1 mmol). After stirring at the same temperature for 10 minutes, the reaction was warmed to 0 °C and stirred for additional 30 minutes. The resulting mixture was then diluted with *t*BuOMe, worked up as usual and purified by flash chromatography (SiO₂).

1.7. General procedure for acetylation of alcohols.

Acetic anhydride (0.2 mmol) was added to a stirred solution of the alcohol substrate (0.1 mmol) and a catalytic amount of DMAP (10 mol%) in pyridine (0.1 mL) at 0 °C. After complete conversion (1 h), the resulting mixture was quenched with 1 drop of MeOH, worked up as usual and purified by flash chromatography (SiO₂) if specified.

2. Preparation and domino reactions of substrate-diol **1i**.

2.1. Preparation of substrate-diol **1i**.

MOM-protection of the known carbinol (1.0 g, 1.99 mmol) was carried out according to general procedure (12h). Purification by flash chromatography (SiO₂, heptane/EtOAc, 95:5) gave the desired MOM-ether (1.02 g, 94%), characterized as a diastereomeric mixture. Colourless oil; IR (film): $\nu = 2927, 1471, 1387, 1250, 1092, 1060, 1035, 879, 860, 772, 700 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; ESIMS (MeOH): 569.4 ($[M + \text{Na}]^+$, 100); HRESIMS: calcd. for $\text{C}_{31}\text{H}_{54}\text{O}_4\text{NaSi}_2$ m/z 569.3458; found: 569.3451.

Fluoride deprotection of the latter (900 mg, 1.65 mmol) using the general procedure (4h) gave after flash chromatography (SiO₂, heptane/EtOAc, 1:1) the substrate-diol **1i** (399 mg, 76%); one diastereomer was separated for characterization purposes.

(11R*)-**1i**: white solid, m.p. = 168-170 °C (heptane-EtOAc); IR (film): $\nu = 3319, 2931, 1456, 1151, 1095, 1045, 1031, 1010, 730, 704 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; ¹H-NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃): $\delta = 0.83\text{-}0.94$ (m, 1 H), 0.99 (dd, $J = 10.9, 13.9$ Hz, 1 H), 1.10 (td, $J = 4.2, 14.0$ Hz, 1 H), 1.43 (qd, $J = 4.2, 13.4$ Hz, 1 H), 1.55 (d, $J = 14.4$ Hz, 1 H), 1.59-1.66 (m, 2 H), 1.87 (qd, $J = 3.6, 13.6$ Hz, 1 H), 1.97 (d, $J = 12.4$ Hz, 1 H), 2.09 (dd, $J = 4.1, 13.9$ Hz, 1 H), 2.23 (d, $J = 14.0$ Hz, 1 H), 1.43 (tdt, $J = 2.2, 4.3, 13.7$ Hz, 1 H), 3.33 (s, 1 H), 4.02 (dt, $J = 2.2, 6.7$ Hz, 1 H), 4.38 (ddd, $J = 3.9, 6.9, 10.7$ Hz, 1 H), 4.41 and 4.44 (ABquartet, $J = 7.0$ Hz, 2 H), 5.16 (s, 1 H), 5.55 (dd $J = 1.6, 2.7$ Hz, 1 H), 7.30-7.35 (m, 1 H), 7.35-7.41 (m, 4 H); ¹³C-NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃): $\delta = 22.3, 28.2, 31.3, 37.8, 38.4, 44.6, 56.0, 71.0, 74.0, 78.1, 94.3, 123.7, 127.7, 128.0$ (2 C), 128.6 (2 C), 138.1, 143.8; ESIMS (MeOH): 341.2 ($[M + \text{Na}]^+$, 100); HRESIMS: m/z calcd. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_4\text{Na}$: 341.1729; found: 341.1725.

2.2. Domino reactions. Synthesis of **2i** and **4i**.

2.2.1. Establishing the diastereomeric ratio (dr) of domino product **2i** (interrupted cascade).

The oxidative cleavage of **1i** (100 mg, 0.31 mmol, diastereomeric mixture), using method A over 4h, afforded after flash chromatography (SiO_2 , heptane/EtOAc, 4:1) 84 mg (85%) of domino product **2i** (dr = 1.2:1).

The oxidative cleavage of **(11R*)-1i** (100 mg, 0.31 mmol), using method A over 4h, afforded after flash chromatography (SiO_2 , heptane/EtOAc, 4:1) 82 mg (82%) of domino product **(11R*)-2i**.

Half-cascade domino product (11R*)-2i: crystals, m.p. = 86-88 °C (*t*BuOMe); IR (film): $\nu = 2933, 2867, 1626, 1453, 1442, 1213, 1152, 1122, 1077, 1020, 938, 782, 702$ cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (500 MHz, CDCl_3): $\delta = 0.65$ (tq, $J = 3.7, 13.8$ Hz, 1 H), 1.02-1.22 (m, 3 H), 1.30 (ddd, $J = 4.3, 14.1, 14.5$ Hz, 1 H), 1.45 (ddd, $J = 12.7, 13.5, 14.0$ Hz, 1 H), 1.75 (d, $J = 14.4$ Hz, 1 H), 1.95 (d, $J = 14.2$ Hz, 1 H), 2.12 (dd, $J = 5.7, 14.2$ Hz, 1 H), 2.54 (d, $J = 14.2$ Hz, 1 H), 3.32 (s, 3 H), 4.42 and 4.44 (ABquartet, $J = 10.1$ Hz, 2 H), 4.92 (s, 1 H), 5.01 (d, $J = 6.2$ Hz, 1 H), 5.62 (d, $J = 5.6$ Hz, 1 H), 6.28 (d, $J = 6.1$ Hz, 1 H), 7.20-7.36 (m, 5 H); $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (125 MHz, CDCl_3): $\delta = 19.6, 21.9, 29.7, 30.1, 50.8, 56.4, 58.0, 79.6, 81.2, 94.6, 98.7, 109.9, 127.9, 128.0$ (2 C), 128.4 (2 C), 139.6, 139.9; ESIMS (MeOH): 339.2 ($[M + \text{Na}]^+$, 100); HRESIMS: m/z calcd. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_4\text{Na}$: 339.1572; found: 339.1569.

2.2.2. Time and Temperature controlled domino transformations.

The oxidative cleavage of **1i** (50 mg, 0.16 mmol, diastereomeric mixture), using method B over 1h, afforded after flash chromatography (SiO_2 , heptane/EtOAc, 4:1) 15.8 mg (32%) of the interrupted cascade domino product **(11S*)-2i** and 20.7 mg (40%) of “Path B” domino product **4i**.

Half-cascade domino product (11S*)-2i: crystals, m.p. = 92-95 °C (*t*BuOMe); IR (film): $\nu = 2948, 2913, 2867, 1726, 1627, 1447, 1213, 1155, 1077, 1013, 937, 778, 718\text{ cm}^{-1}$; $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (500 MHz, $CDCl_3$): $\delta = 1.21$ (td, $J = 3.9, 14.2\text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 1.43-1.52 (m, 2 H), 1.60-1.71 (m, 3 H), 1.90-2.00 (m, 1 H), 2.06 (dd, $J = 5.0, 8.0\text{ Hz}$, 2 H), 2.21 (d, $J = 13.9\text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 3.42 (s, 3 H), 4.49 and 4.45 (ABquartet, $J = 6.7\text{ Hz}$, 2 H), 5.08-5.11 (m, 2 H), 5.61 (d, $J = 5.6\text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 6.36 (d, $J = 6.1\text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 7.28-7.32 (m, 1 H), 7.32-7.28 (m, 4 H); $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (125 MHz, $CDCl_3$): $\delta = 20.7, 22.2, 30.5, 30.8, 48.9, 56.3, 57.0, 83.2, 83.7, 95.2, 99.0, 109.4, 127.6, 127.9$ (2 C), 128.3 (2 C), 139.6, 140.3; ESIMS (MeOH): 339.2 ($[M + Na]^+$, 100); HRESIMS: m/z calcd. for $C_{19}H_{24}O_4Na$: 339.1572; found: 339.1565.

Domino product (11R*)-4i: white solid, m.p. = 150-151 °C (*t*BuOMe); IR (film): $\nu = 2937, 2864, 1735, 1451, 1374, 1240, 1141, 1050, 1017, 951, 907, 724\text{ cm}^{-1}$; $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (500 MHz, $CDCl_3$): $\delta = 1.25-1.37$ (m, 1 H), 1.45 (dd, $J = 4.9, 14.4\text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 1.49-1.62 (m, 2 H), 1.66-1.78 (m, 2 H), 1.78-1.88 (m, 1 H), 2.02 (d, $J = 14.5\text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 2.12-2.19 (m, 4 H), 2.44 (d, $J = 14.9\text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 3.92 (s, 1 H), 5.08 (s, 1 H), 5.54 (d, $J = 4.8\text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 6.18 (s, 1 H), 7.30-7.35 (m, 1 H), 7.36-7.41 (m, 4 H); $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (125 MHz, $CDCl_3$): $\delta = 20.8, 21.3$ (2 C), 31.6, 32.1, 44.4, 51.0, 81.5, 82.0, 87.9, 90.5, 98.6, 126.2 (2 C), 127.7, 128.1 (2 C), 138.3, 170.0; ESIMS (MeOH): 353.1 ($[M + Na]^+$, 100); HRESIMS: calcd. for $C_{19}H_{22}O_5Na$ m/z 353.1365; found: 353.1367.

Domino reaction over (11S*)-2i (32 mg, 0.1 mmol) using method C afforded after flash chromatography (SiO₂, heptane/EtOAc, 4:1) 20.4 mg (61%) of “Path B” domino product (11S*)-4i.

Domino product (11S*)-4i: white solid, m.p. = 91-93 °C (*t*BuOMe); IR (film): $\nu = 2942, 2867, 1742, 1452, 1371, 1232, 1145, 1053, 953, 795, 748, 705 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; ¹H-NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃): $\delta = 1.12\text{-}1.22 \text{ (m, 2 H)}, 1.35\text{-}1.50 \text{ (m, 2 H)}, 1.58\text{-}1.69 \text{ (m, 3 H)}, 2.16 \text{ (s, 3 H)}, 2.20\text{-}2.30 \text{ (m, 2 H)}, 2.33 \text{ (d, } J = 13.5 \text{ Hz, 1 H)}, 4.22 \text{ (s, 1 H)}, 5.36 \text{ (s, 1 H)}, 5.66 \text{ (d, } J = 3.8 \text{ Hz, 1 H)}, 6.12 \text{ (s, 1 H)}, 7.25\text{-}7.32 \text{ (m, 3 H)}, 7.35\text{-}7.39 \text{ (m, 2 H)}$; ¹³C-NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃): $\delta = 17.7, 18.5, 21.4, 30.0, 30.1, 49.9, 51.7, 82.9, 87.9, 90.7, 91.5, 98.6, 125.9 \text{ (2 C)}, 127.6, 128.2 \text{ (2 C)}, 140.4, 170.0$; ESIMS (MeOH): 353.1 ($[M + \text{Na}]^+$, 100); HRESIMS: m/z calcd. for C₁₉H₂₂O₅Na: 353.1365; found: 353.1369.

3. Preparation and domino reactions of substrate-diol 1j.

3.1. Preparation of substrate-diol 1j.

MOM-protection of the known carbinol (1.0 g, 1.87 mmol) was carried out according to general procedure (12h). Purification by flash chromatography (SiO₂, heptane/EtOAc, 95:5) afforded the desired MOM-ether (785 mg, 72%), characterized as a diastereomeric mixture. Colourless oil; IR (film): $\nu = 2927, 2854, 1612, 1583, 1511, 1462, 1386, 1360, 1247, 1092, 1063, 1028, 820, 771 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; ESIMS (MeOH): 599.4 ($[M + \text{Na}]^+$, 100); HRESIMS: m/z calcd. for C₃₂H₅₆O₅NaSi₂: 599.3666; found: 599.3662. Fluoride deprotection of the latter (800 g, 1.39 mmol) using the general procedure (1h) gave after flash chromatography (SiO₂, heptane/EtOAc, 1:1) the substrate-diol **1j** (338 mg, 70%), characterized as a diastereomeric mixture. Colourless oil; IR (film): $\nu = 3381, 2928, 1585, 1488, 1242, 1023, 908, 728 \text{ cm}^{-1}$;

ESIMS (MeOH+CH₂Cl₂): 371.1 ([M + Na]⁺, 100); HRESIMS: *m/z* calcd. for C₂₀H₂₈O₅Na: 371.1921; found: 371.1927.

3.2. Domino reactions. Synthesis of **2j** and **4j**.

3.2.1. Establishing the diastereomeric ratio (dr) of domino product **2j** (interrupted cascade).

The oxidative cleavage of **1j** (20 mg, 0.057 mmol, diastereomeric mixture), using method A over 4h, afforded after flash chromatography (SiO₂, heptane/EtOAc, 4:1) 16 mg (80%) of domino product **2j** (dr = 5:1). The major compound is described.

Half-cascade domino product (11*S*^{*})-2j****: colourless oil; IR (film): $\nu = 2925, 1628, 1489, 1240, 1175, 1024, 941, 755 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; ¹H-NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃): $\delta = 1.20\text{-}1.23$ (m, 1 H), 1.36 (dd, $J = 5.9, 13.9 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 1.45-1.49 (m, 2 H), 1.63 (bs, 2 H), 1.84 (d, $J = 14.3 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 2.03 (m, 2 H), 2.56 (d, $J = 14.0 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 3.37 (s, 3 H), 3.81 (s, 3 H), 4.35 and 4.39 (ABquartet, $J = 6.6 \text{ Hz}$, 2 H), 5.03 (d, $J = 6.1 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 5.56 (d, $J = 5.5 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 5.63 (s, 1 H), 6.31 (d, $J = 6.0 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 6.87 (d, $J = 8.2 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 6.98 (t, $J = 7.4 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 7.24-7.25 (m, 1 H), 7.42 (d, $J = 7.5 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H); ¹³C-NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃): $\delta = 20.8, 22.3, 30.8$ (2 C), 46.6, 55.3, 56.8, 56.9, 75.4, 83.3, 95.3, 99.4, 109.6, 110.6, 120.1, 127.8, 128.5, 129.9, 140.0, 157.1; ESIMS (MeOH): 369.2 ([M + Na]⁺, 100); HRESIMS: *m/z* calcd. for C₂₀H₂₆O₅Na: 369.1678; found: 369.1682.

3.2.2. Time and Temperature controlled domino transformations.

Oxidative cleavage of **1j** (40 mg, 0.115 mmol, diastereomeric mixture), using method B over 2h, afforded after flash chromatography (SiO_2 , heptane/EtOAc, 4:1) 8.7 mg (22%) of a diastereomeric mixture of interrupted cascade domino product **2j** and 17.8 mg (43%) of “Path B” domino product ($11S^*$)-**4j**. When using method C - MW heating at $90^\circ C$, 5 min- on 20 mg (0.057 mmol), 16.3 mg (79%) of “Path B” domino product ($11S^*$)-**4j** were obtained. The major compound is described.

Domino product ($11S^*$)-4j: crystals, m.p. = $61-63^\circ C$ (Et_2O); IR (film): $\nu = 2942, 1742, 1491, 1371, 1239, 1141, 1050, 938, 755, cm^{-1}$; 1H -NMR (500 MHz, $CDCl_3$): $\delta = 1.02-1.04$ (m, 2 H), $1.22-1.26$ (m, 2 H), $1.41-1.46$ (m, 1 H), $1.55-1.58$ (m, 1 H), $1.66-1.69$ (m, 1 H), $2.05-2.09$ (m, 2 H), 2.13 (s, 3 H), 2.43 (d, $J = 13.2$ Hz, 1 H), 3.82 (s, 3 H), 4.11 (s, 1 H), 5.62 (s, 1 H), 5.66 (d, $J = 3.4$ Hz, 1 H), 6.05 (s, 1 H), 6.86 (d, $J = 8.1$ Hz, 1 H), 6.98 (t, $J = 7.4$ Hz, 1 H), $7.25-7.27$ (m, 1 H), 7.37 (d, $J = 7.1$ Hz, 1 H); ^{13}C -NMR (125 MHz, $CDCl_3$): $\delta = 16.1, 16.5, 21.4, 27.2, 28.1, 47.7, 48.2, 55.1, 82.6, 86.9, 88.6, 92.5, 99.3, 109.9, 120.5, 126.0, 128.2, 128.7, 156.1, 170.1$; ESIMS (MeOH): 383.1 ($[M + Na]^+$, 100); HRESIMS: m/z calcd. for $C_{20}H_{24}O_6Na$: 383.1471; found: 383.1466.

4. Preparation and domino reactions of substrate-diol **1k**.

4.1. Preparation of substrate-diol **1k**.

MOM-protection of the known carbinol (1.5 g, 2.67 mmol) was carried out according to general procedure (4h). Purification by flash chromatography (SiO_2 , heptane/EtOAc, 9:1) afforded the desired MOM-ether (1.6 g, 98%), characterized as a diastereomeric mixture. Colourless oil; IR (film): $\nu = 2929$, 2854, 1611, 1586, 1504, 1463, 1255, 1209, 1157, 1090, 1030, 820, 774 cm^{-1} ; ESIMS (MeOH): 629.4 ($[M + \text{Na}]^+$, 100); HRESIMS: calcd. for $\text{C}_{33}\text{H}_{58}\text{O}_6\text{NaSi}_2$ m/z 629.3670; found: 629.3663.

Fluoride deprotection of the latter (1.6 g, 2.6 mmol) using the general procedure (4h) afforded after flash chromatography (SiO_2 , heptane/EtOAc, 1:1) the substrate-diol **1k** (620 mg, 62%), characterized as a diastereomeric mixture. Colourless oil; IR (film): $\nu = 3384$, 2930, 2359, 1609, 1585, 1504, 1453, 1292, 1257, 1208, 1152, 1091, 1023, 910, 831, 729 cm^{-1} ; ESIMS (MeOH): 401.2 ($[M + \text{Na}]^+$, 100); HRESIMS: m/z calcd. for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}_6\text{Na}$: 401.1940; found: 401.1937.

4.2. Domino reactions. Synthesis of **2k** and **4k**.

4.2.1. Establishing the diastereomeric ratio (dr) of domino product **2k** (interrupted cascade).

The oxidative cleavage of **1k** (50 mg, 0.132 mmol, diastereomeric mixture), using method A over 4h, afforded after flash chromatography (SiO_2 , heptane/EtOAc, 4:1) 43 mg (87%) of product **2k** (dr = 7:1). The major compound is described.

Half-cascade domino product (11S*)-2k: colourless oil; IR (film): $\nu = 2935, 1715, 1609, 1504, 1461, 1301, 1208, 1024, 940, 833 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (500 MHz, CDCl_3): $\delta = 1.22$ (td, $J = 3.2, 14.0 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 1.39 (dd, $J = 5.8, 13.9 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 1.46 (dt, $J = 3.3, 12.6 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 1.62 - 1.71 (m, 2 H), 1.85 (d, $J = 14.5 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 1.90 - 1.99 (m, 1 H), 2.03 (dd, $J = 5.2, 7.7 \text{ Hz}$, 2 H), 2.52 (d, $J = 14.0 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 3.39 (s, 3 H), 3.80 (s, 3 H), 3.83 (s, 3 H), 4.38 (A_2s , 2 H), 5.05 (d, $J = 6.1 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 5.56 (s, 1 H), 5.58 (d, $J = 5.6 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 6.32 (d, $J = 5.9 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 6.45 (d, $J = 2.1 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 6.55 (dd, $J = 2.1, 8.4$, 1 H), 7.33 (d, $J = 8.4 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H); $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (125 MHz, CDCl_3): $\delta = 20.8, 22.3, 30.8$ (2 C), $46.7, 55.3$ (2 C), 57.0 (2 C), $75.2, 83.2, 95.1, 98.0, 99.4, 104.3, 109.6, 120.1, 130.5, 139.9, 158.2, 160.0$; ESIMS (MeOH): 399.2 ($[M + \text{Na}]^+$, 100); HRESIMS: m/z calcd. for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}_6\text{Na}$: 399.1784 ; found: 399.1787 .

4.2.2. Time and Temperature controlled domino transformations.

The oxidative cleavage of **1k** (20 mg, 0.053 mmol, diastereomeric mixture), using method B over 30h, afforded after flash chromatography (SiO_2 , heptane/EtOAc, 4:1) 8.9 mg (45%) of the interrupted cascade **(11S*)-2k** and 4.1 mg (20%) of a diastereomeric mixture of “Path B” domino products **4k**; when using method C on 20 mg (0.053 mmol), 13.8 mg (67%) of a diastereomeric mixture of “Path B” domino products **4k** were obtained. The major compound is described.

Domino product 4k: colourless oil; IR (film): $\nu = 2937, 1740, 1612, 1588, 1505, 1455, 1371, 1238, 1207, 1143, 1051, 940, 831, 735 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (500 MHz, CDCl_3): $\delta = 1.45$ - 1.49 (m, 2 H), 1.53 - 1.59 (m, 3 H), 1.63 - 1.70 (m, 2 H), 2.05 - 2.09 (m, 2 H), 2.16 (s, 3 H), 2.38 (d, $J = 12.7 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 3.81 (s, 3 H), 3.83 (s, 3 H), 4.17 (s, 1 H), 5.57 (s, 1 H), 5.65 (d, $J = 3.6 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 6.06 (s, 1 H), 6.46 (s, 2 H), 7.23 (s, 1 H); $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (125 MHz, CDCl_3): $\delta = 16.7, 17.1, 21.8, 27.2, 27.9, 47.8, 49.1, 55.5, 55.7, 82.9, 87.2, 89.0, 92.8, 98.6, 99.6, 104.2, 126.9, 150.3, 160.4, 160.7, 170.7$; ESIMS (MeOH): 413.2 ($[M + \text{Na}]^+$, 100); HRESIMS: m/z calcd. for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_7\text{Na}$: 413.1576 ; found: 413.1573 .

5. Preparation and domino reactions of substrate-diol **11**.

5.1. Preparation of substrate-diol **11**.

MOM-protection of the known carbinol (300 mg, 0.7 mmol) was carried out according to general procedure (12h). Purification by flash chromatography (SiO_2 , heptane/EtOAc, 95:5) afforded the desired MOM-ether (320 mg, 92%), characterized as a diastereomeric mixture. Colourless oil; IR (film): $\nu = 2928, 1596, 1461, 1253, 1204, 1154, 1061, 923, 833, 774, 669 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; ESIMS (MeOH): 517.3 ($[M + \text{Na}]^+$, 100); HRESIMS: m/z calcd. for $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}_4\text{NaSi}_2$: 517.3248; found: 517.3257.

Fluoride deprotection of the latter (300 mg, 0.60 mmol) using the general procedure (1h) gave after flash chromatography (SiO_2 , heptane/EtOAc, 1:1) the substrate-diol **11** (140 mg, 89%), characterized as a diastereomeric mixture. IR (film): $\nu = 3384, 2930, 1609, 1585, 1504, 1453, 1292, 1257, 1152, 1091, 1023, 910, 831, 729 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; ESIMS (MeOH): 289.1 ($[M + \text{Na}]^+$, 100); HRESIMS: m/z calcd. for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_4\text{Na}$: 289.1518, found: 289.1524.

5.2. Domino reactions. Synthesis of **21** and **41**.

5.2.1. Establishing the diastereomeric ratio (dr) of domino product **21** (interrupted cascade).

The oxidative cleavage of **11** (140 mg, 0.52 mmol, diastereomeric mixture), using method A over 4 h, afforded after flash chromatography (SiO_2 , heptane/EtOAc, 4:1) 108 mg (79%) of domino product **21** (dr = 2.5:1) as a diastereomeric mixture. The major compound is described.

Half-cascade domino product 21: colourless oil; IR (film): $\nu = 2930, 1627, 1443, 1212, 1157, 1056, 1018, 941, 896 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (500 MHz, CDCl_3): $\delta = 1.40\text{-}1.49$ (m, 2 H), 1.51-1.86 (m, 2 H), 1.65-1.75 (m, 2 H), 1.94-1.99 (m, 2 H), 2.05-2.07 (m, 1 H), 2.20-2.25 (m, 1 H), 2.44 (d, $J = 2.2 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 3.39 (s, 3 H), 4.54 (d, $J = 7.1 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 4.77 (s, 1 H), 4.83 (d, $J = 6.7 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 4.93 (d, $J = 7.3 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 5.59 (d, $J = 5.3 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 6.24 (d, $J = 5.9 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H); $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (125 MHz, CDCl_3): $\delta = 20.3, 22.4, 31.0, 31.7, 49.7, 56.5, 72.1, 75.2, 77.5, 81.0, 82.1, 94.4, 98.8, 108.5, 140.6$; ESIMS (MeOH): 287.1 ($[M + \text{Na}]^+$, 100); HRESIMS: m/z calcd. for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_4\text{Na}$: 287.1261; found: 287.1259.

5.2.2. Conventional domino transformation.

The oxidative cleavage of **11** (40 mg, 0.151 mmol, diastereomeric mixture), using method B over 6h, afforded after flash chromatography (SiO_2 , heptane/EtOAc, 4:1) 29.3 mg (70%) of “Path B” domino product **41** (dr = 2.5:1) as a diastereomeric mixture. The major compound is described.

Domino product 41: colourless oil; IR (film): $\nu = 2931, 1741, 1376, 1237, 1144, 1049, 951, 780, \text{cm}^{-1}$; $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (500 MHz, CDCl_3): $\delta = 1.25\text{-}1.29$ (m, 1 H), 1.33-1.39 (m, 1 H), 1.45-1.49 (m, 2 H), 1.58-1.60 (m, 2 H), 1.89-1.92 (m, 1 H), 2.10 (s, 3 H), 2.32 (d, $J = 15.7 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 2.54 (d, $J = 16.8 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 2.65 (d, $J = 5.1 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 3.97 (s, 1 H), 4.77 (s, 1 H), 5.29 (s, 1 H), 5.54 (d, $J = 5.2 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 5.97 (s, 1 H); $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (125 MHz, CDCl_3): $\delta = 19.4, 21.5, 21.6, 30.9, 31.8, 32.7, 49.9, 52.9, 53.7, 72.7, 82.0, 87.7, 90.5, 98.7, 170.3$. ESIMS (MeOH): 301.1 ($[M + \text{Na}]^+$, 100); HRESIMS: m/z calcd. for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_5\text{Na}$: 301.1154; found: 301.1156.

6. Domino reactions of substrate-diol **1b**. Synthesis of (11*S*^{*})-**4b**.

The oxidative cleavage of **1b** (220 mg, 0.63 mmol, diastereomeric mixture, dr = 4:1), using method B over 5h, afforded after flash chromatography (SiO₂, heptane/EtOAc, 4:1) 37.2 mg (17%) of the single diastereomeric compound (11*S*^{*})-**2b** and 147.5 mg (65%) of “Path B” domino compound (11*R*^{*})-**4b**.

Half-cascade domino product (11*S*^{*})-2b**:** colourless oil; IR (film): $\nu = 2927, 2856, 1641, 1356, 1324, 1161, 1120, 1001, 968, 929, 902, 819, 781, 753, 740, 697, 661\text{ cm}^{-1}$; ¹H-NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃): $\delta = 1.18$ (td, $J = 3.9, 13.9$ Hz, 1 H), 1.35-1.55 (m, 2 H), 1.56-1.73 (m, 3 H), 1.81-1.98 (m, 1 H), 2.00-2.06 (m, 2 H), 2.19 (d, $J = 13.9$ Hz, 1 H), 3.41 (s, 3 H), 3.80 (s, 3 H), 4.47 and 4.43 (ABquartet, $J = 6.4$ Hz, 2 H), 5.03 (s, 1 H), 5.07 (d, $J = 6.1$ Hz, 1 H), 5.59 (d, $J = 5.4$ Hz, 1 H), 6.33 (d, $J = 6.1$ Hz, 1 H), 6.81 (dd, $J = 2.6, 8.2$ Hz, 1 H), 6.86-6.93 (m, 2 H), 7.24 (t, $J = 7.8$ Hz, 1 H); ¹³C-NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃): $\delta = 20.6, 22.1, 30.5, 30.8, 49.0, 55.2, 56.3, 57.0, 83.1, 83.6, 95.2, 98.9, 109.3, 112.5, 114.3, 120.7, 128.9, 140.3, 141.2, 159.3$; ESIMS (MeOH): 369.2 ($[M + Na]^+$, 100); HRESIMS: m/z calcd. for C₂₀H₂₆O₅Na: 369.1678; found: 369.1682.

Application of conventional domino conditions to the previously obtained (11*S*^{*})-**2b** (37 mg, 0.107 mmol), using method B over 16h, afforded “Path A” domino compound **3b** (14.1 mg, 44%) and “Path B” domino compound (11*S*^{*})-**4b** (12.7 mg, 33%).

Domino product (11*S*^{*})-4b**:** colourless oil; IR (film): $\nu = 2943, 1740, 1601, 1585, 1454, 1238, 1142, 1049, 939, 728 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; ¹H-NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃): $\delta = 0.53\text{-}0.61$ (m, 1 H), 1.12-1.17 (m, 2 H), 1.36-1.46 (m, 2 H), 1.57-1.68 (m, 1 H), 2.13 (s, 3 H), 2.18-2.31 (m, 4 H), 3.82 (s, 3 H), 4.18 (s, 1 H), 5.31 (s, 1 H), 5.63 (d, $J = 3.8 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 6.09 (s, 1 H), 6.80-6.83 (m, 3 H), 7.24-7.27 (m, 1 H); ¹³C-NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃): $\delta = 17.6, 18.5, 21.4, 29.9, 30.0, 49.9, 51.6, 55.3, 83.0, 88.0, 90.6, 91.5, 98.6, 111.9, 112.6, 118.4, 129.2, 142.1, 159.6, 170.0$; ESIMS (MeOH): 383.2 ($[M + \text{Na}]^+$, 100); HRESIMS: m/z calcd. for C₂₀H₂₄O₆Na: 383.1471; found: 383.1475.

7. Domino reactions of substrate-diol **1c**. Synthesis of (11*S*^{*})-**4c**.

Oxidative cleavage of **1c** (260 mg, 0.69 mmol, diastereomeric mixture, dr = 3.3:1), using method B over 5h, afforded after flash chromatography (SiO₂, heptane/EtOAc, 4:1) 69.8 mg (27%) of the single diastereomer (11*S*^{*})-**2c** and 129.2 (48%) of domino compound (11*R*^{*})-**4c**.

Application of conventional domino conditions to the previously obtained (11*S*^{*})-**2c** (69 mg, 0.18 mmol), using method B over 36h, afforded “Path A” domino compound **3c** (35.0 mg, 58%) and “Path B” domino compound (11*S*^{*})-**4c** (3.6 mg, 5%).

Domino product (11*S*^{*})-4c****: colourless oil; IR (film): $\nu = 2926, 2852, 1739, 1598, 1460, 1372, 1241, 1154, 1052, 944, 906, 727 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; ¹H-NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃): $\delta = 0.61\text{-}0.72$ (m, 1 H), 1.14-1.22 (m, 3 H), 1.37-1.50 (m, 2 H), 1.58-1.71 (m, 2 H), 2.14 (s, 2 H), 2.17-2.25 (m, 2 H), 2.28 (d, *J* = 13.3 Hz, 1 H), 3.80 (s, 6 H), 4.16 (s, 1 H), 5.27 (s, 1 H), 5.63 (d, *J* = 3.8 Hz, 1 H), 6.08 (s, 1 H), 6.38 (d, *J* = 2.2 Hz, 1 H), 6.40 (d, *J* = 2.1 Hz, 2 H); ¹³C-NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃): $\delta = 17.6, 18.4, 29.7$ (2 C), 29.8, 29.9, 50.0, 51.5, 55.4, 83.0, 88.0, 90.8, 91.5, 98.7, 99.1, 104.3 (2 C), 143.0, 160.7 (2 C), 170.0; ESIMS (CH₃CN): 454.2 ([*M* + Na + CH₃CN]⁺, 100); HRESIMS: *m/z* calcd. for C₂₃H₂₉NO₇Na: 454.1842; found: 454.1840.

8. Domino reactions of substrate-diol **1d**. Synthesis of (11*S*^{*})-**4d**.

The oxidative cleavage of **1d** (115 mg, 0.28 mmol, diastereomeric mixture, dr = 2.5:1), using method B

over 5h, afforded after flash chromatography (SiO₂, heptane/EtOAc, 4:1) 38.9 mg (34%) of the single diastereomer (11*S**)-2d and 34.1 mg (29%) of “Path B” domino compound (11*R**)-4d.

Application of conventional domino conditions to the previously obtained (11*S**)-2d (39 mg, 0.095 mmol), using method B over 36h, afforded “Path A” domino compound 3b (20.9 mg, 61%) and “Path B” domino compound (11*S**)-4d (9.6 mg, 24%).

Domino product (11*S)-4d:** colourless oil; IR (film): $\square\square = 2938, 1741, 1591, 1416, 1331, 1233, 1125, 1008, 944, 802, 728 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; ¹H-NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃): $\square\square = 0.62\text{-}0.74 \text{ (m, 1 H)}, 1.15\text{-}1.24 \text{ (m, 2 H)}, 1.41\text{-}1.46 \text{ (m, 2 H)}, 1.57\text{-}1.66 \text{ (m, 2 H)}, 2.14 \text{ (s, 3 H)}, 2.19\text{-}2.24 \text{ (m, 2 H)}, 2.29 \text{ (d, } J = 13.4 \text{ Hz, 1 H)}, 3.85 \text{ (s, 3 H)}, 3.86 \text{ (s, 6 H)}, 4.17 \text{ (s, 1 H)}, 5.28 \text{ (s, 1 H)}, 5.64 \text{ (d, } J = 3.8 \text{ Hz, 1 H)}, 6.08 \text{ (s, 1 H)}, 6.46 \text{ (s, 2 H)}$; ¹³C-NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃): $\square\square = 17.5, 18.3, 21.4, 29.9 \text{ (3 C)}, 50.0, 51.4, 56.2 \text{ (2 C)}, 61.0, 83.1, 88.0, 90.9, 91.5, 98.6, 103.1 \text{ (2 C)}, 136.0, 153.2 \text{ (2 C)}, 170.0$; ESIMS (MeOH): 443.2 ($[M + Na]^+$, 100); HRMS (ESI): m/z calcd. for C₂₂H₂₈O₈Na: 443.1682; found: 443.1692.

9. Preparation and domino reactions of substrate-diol 1'c.

9.1. Preparation of substrate-diol 1'c.

Xanthate was prepared from the known carbinol (2.1 g, 3.73 mmol) according to general procedure; after

purification by flash chromatography (SiO₂, heptane/EtOAc, 95:5) the desired compound was obtained (1.92 g, 79%) and characterized as a diastereomeric mixture. Yellow oil; IR (film): $\nu = 2929, 2855, 1591, 1461, 1250, 1204, 1156, 1064, 835, 775 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; ESIMS (MeOH): 675.3 ($[M + \text{Na}]^+$, 100); HRESIMS: m/z calcd. for C₃₃H₅₆O₅S₂Si₂Na: 675.3005; found: 675.3007.

Deoxygenation of the xanthate according to the general procedure, starting from 1.90 g (2.91 mmol), provided after purification by flash chromatography (SiO₂, heptane/EtOAc, 95:5) the deoxygenated TBS-protected diol (1.51 g, 95%). One diastereomer was separated for characterization purposes.

1'c-TBS: colourless oil; IR (film): $\nu = 2930, 2845, 1590, 1470, 1255, 1201, 1059, 1012, 920, 833, 684 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; ¹H-NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃): $\delta = -0.05$ (s, 3 H), -0.04 (s, 3 H), 0.05 (s, 3 H), 0.09 (s, 3 H), 0.84 (s, 9 H), 0.89 (s, 9 H), 1.18 - 1.42 (m, 5 H), 1.55 - 1.62 (m, 1 H), 1.63 - 1.68 (m, 1 H), 1.74 (d, $J = 12.6$ Hz, 1 H), 1.79 (dd, $J = 4.0, 13.6$ Hz, 1 H), 1.89 (d, $J = 12.2$ Hz, 1 H), 2.13 (d, $J = 13.4$ Hz, 1 H), 2.39 (t, $J = 13.7$ Hz, 1 H), 2.57 (d, $J = 13.7$ Hz, 1

H), 2.98 (d, $J = 13.8$ Hz, 1 H), 3.30 (ddd, $J = 4.3, 6.6, 11.4$ Hz, 1 H), 3.76 (s, 6 H), 3.94 (dt, $J = 2.1, 6.5$ Hz, 1 H), 5.25 (s, 1 H), 6.33 (m, 3 H); ¹³C-NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃): $\delta = -4.2$ (2 C), $-4.1, -3.9, 17.9, 18.1, 22.1, 26.0$ (3 C), 26.1 (3 C), $28.6, 31.9, 41.3, 41.4, 41.8, 43.1, 55.2$ (2 C), $70.9, 74.6, 97.8, 108.8$ (2 C), $124.3, 141.5, 143.2, 160.3$ (2 C); ESIMS (MeOH): 569.2 ($[M + \text{Na}]^+$, 100).

Fluoride deprotection of the latter (1.5 g, 2.74 mmol) using the general procedure (5h) gave after flash chromatography (SiO₂, heptane/EtOAc, 1:1) the substrate-diol **1'c** (533 mg, 61%). One diastereomer was separated for characterization purposes.

1'c: colourless oil; IR (film): $\nu = 3385, 2927, 2856, 2357, 1594, 1456, 1203, 1150, 1058, 837 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; ¹H-NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃): $\delta = 1.00$ (td, $J = 3.5, 13.9$ Hz, 1 H), 1.13 (t, $J = 12.7$ Hz, 1 H), 1.25 - 1.39 (m, 1 H), 1.57 (dd, $J = 13.7$ Hz, 1 H), 1.67 - 1.91 (m, 3 H), 2.10 (d, $J = 13.9$ Hz, 1 H), 2.29 (t, $J = 13.9$ Hz, 1 H), 2.66 (d, $J = 13.6$ Hz, 1 H), 2.86 (d, $J = 13.5$ Hz, 1 H), 3.55 - 3.63 (m, 3 H), 3.73 (s, 6 H), 4.01 (dt, $J = 2.2, 7.6$ Hz, 1 H), 5.24 (s, 1 H), 6.33 (m, 3 H); ¹³C-NMR

(75 MHz, CDCl₃): $\delta = 21.7, 28.2, 31.4, 38.5, 40.0, 40.9, 41.2, 55.2$ (2 C), $70.2, 74.6, 97.8, 108.8$ (2 C), $122.2, 140.8, 145.4, 160.2$ (2 C); ESIMS (MeOH): 341.2 ($[M + \text{Na}]^+$, 100); HRESIMS: m/z calcd. for C₁₉H₂₆O₄Na: 341.1729; found: 341.1735.

9.2. Domino reactions. Synthesis of 2'c, 5c, 8c and 9c.

9.2.1. Interrupted cascade.

The oxidative cleavage of **1'c** (160 mg, 0.503 mmol, diastereomeric mixture), using method A over 4h afforded after flash chromatography (SiO_2 , heptane/EtOAc, 4:1) 139.9 mg (88%) of domino product **2'c**.

Half-cascade domino product 2'c: white solid, m.p. = 103-105 °C (*t*BuOMe); IR (film): $\nu = 2910, 1630, 1580, 1340, 1313, 1250, 1120, 900, 720 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (300 MHz, CDCl_3): $\delta = 1.20\text{-}1.28$ (m, 1 H), 1.35-1.50 (m, 3 H), 1.51-1.62 (m, 3 H), 1.79 (dd, $J = 5.7, 13.7$ Hz, 1 H), 2.03 (d, $J = 11.8$ Hz, 1 H), 2.36 (d, $J = 13.7$ Hz, 1 H), 2.65 (d, $J = 13.3$ Hz, 1 H), 2.91 (d, $J = 13.2$ Hz, 1 H), 3.76 (s, 6 H), 4.86 (d, $J = 6.0$ Hz, 1 H), 5.66 (d, $J = 5.5$ Hz, 1 H), 6.26 (d, $J = 6.0$ Hz, 1 H), 6.29-6.34 (m, 3 H); $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (75 MHz, CDCl_3): $\delta = 20.6, 21.1, 29.2, 31.1, 36.4, 48.5, 53.8, 55.1$ (2 C), 82.2, 97.7, 99.3, 108.0 (2 C), 109.9, 139.5, 141.7, 160.4 (2 C); ESIMS (MeOH): 317.2 ($[M + \text{H}]^+$, 100); HRESIMS: m/z calcd. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{25}\text{O}_4$: 317.1753; found: 317.1759.

9.2.2. Domino product.

Applying domino conditions on **2'c** (75 mg, 0.24 mmol), using method D over 20h, afforded after flash chromatography (SiO_2 , heptane/EtOAc, 2:1) 63.0 mg of deoxygenated full cascade **5c** (71%).

Domino product 5c: white solid, mp: 113-116 °C (*t*BuOMe); IR (film): $\nu = 2935, 1737, 1606, 1595, 1492, 1457, 1364, 1234, 1168, 1146, 1055, 919 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (500 MHz, C_6D_6): $\delta = 0.98$ (q, $J = 13.9$ Hz, 1 H), 1.13-1.24 (m, 3 H), 1.27-1.36 (m, 2 H), 1.59-1.66 (m, 1 H), 1.71 (dd, $J = 5.5, 13.7$ Hz, 1 H), 1.81 (s, 3 H), 1.94 (d, $J = 13.8$ Hz, 1 H), 2.07 (d, $J = 14.2$ Hz, 1 H), 2.55 (d, $J = 17.8$ Hz, 1 H), 2.69 (d, $J = 17.8$ Hz, 1 H), 3.29 (s, 3 H), 3.43 (s, 3 H), 3.56 (d, $J = 2.7$ Hz, 1 H), 5.51 (d, $J = 5.5$ Hz, 1 H), 6.19 (d, $J = 2.2$ Hz, 1 H), 6.25 (d, $J = 2.4$ Hz, 1 H), 6.59 (d, $J = 3.2$ Hz, 1 H); $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (125 MHz, C_6D_6): $\delta = 18.2, 18.4, 19.2, 30.3, 33.4, 35.4, 36.9, 42.8, 47.2, 51.8, 52.0, 77.6, 90.0, 94.1, 94.7, 101.8, 113.7, 133.8, 156.2, 157.2, 166.2$; ESIMS (MeOH): 315.2 ($[M - \text{OAc}]^+$, 100), 397.2 ($[M + \text{Na}]^+$, 40); HRESIMS: m/z calcd. for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_6\text{Na}$: 397.1627; found: 397.1637.

Domino reaction over **2'c** (40 mg, 0.13 mmol) following method C –microwaves heating at 70 °C– gave after flash chromatography (SiO_2 , heptane/EtOAc, 4:1) a diastereomeric mixture (R^*/S^* , 2:1) of aldehyde **8c** (16.6 mg, 35%) and the pentacyclic acetal **9c** (9.6 mg, 25%). For **8c**, the major diastereomer was isolated and characterized.

Domino product (2R*)-8c: colourless crystals, m.p. = 157-159 °C (heptane); IR (film): $\nu = 2925, 2853, 1725, 1608, 1598, 1495, 1462, 1233, 1150, 1118, 982 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (500 MHz, CDCl_3): $\delta = 1.19$ -1.27 (m, 2 H), 1.47-1.51 (m, 2 H), 1.74 (d, $J = 14.3$ Hz, 1 H), 1.93 (td, $J = 4.0, 14.3$ Hz, 1 H), 2.07 (s, 3 H), 2.08-2.11 (m, 1 H), 2.21 (dt, $J = 3.1, 13.6$ Hz, 1 H), 2.29-2.37 (m, 2 H), 2.92 (d, $J = 15.4$ Hz, 1 H), 3.72-3.75 (m, 4 H), 3.80 (s, 3 H), 3.78-3.84 (m, 1 H), 6.29 (d, $J = 2.6$ Hz, 1 H), 6.33 (d, $J = 2.6$ Hz, 1 H), 6.37 (dd, $J = 5.3, 6.6$ Hz, 1 H), 9.34 (d, $J = 3.2$ Hz, 1 H); $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (125 MHz, CDCl_3): $\delta = 20.7, 21.5, 22.8, 29.7, 35.2, 40.7, 41.4, 44.7, 51.7, 55.3, 55.4, 85.6, 96.5, 97.6, 104.8, 111.0, 137.6, 158.4, 160.0, 170.3, 199.3$; ESIMS (MeOH): 315.2 ($[M - \text{AcO}]^+$, 100); HRESIMS: m/z calcd. for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_6\text{Na}$: 397.1627; found: 397.1619.

Domino product 9c: crystals, m.p. = 156-158 °C (*t*BuOMe); IR (film): ν = 2931, 2855, 1605, 1458, 1210, 1149, 1087, 1034, 944, 862 cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (500 MHz, CDCl_3): δ = 1.46-1.50 (m, 2 H), 1.57-1.63 (m, 2 H), 1.69-1.71 (m, 3 H), 1.72-1.75 (m, 2 H), 2.02 (d, J = 14.1 Hz, 1 H), 2.75 (d, J = 17.8 Hz, 1 H), 3.11 (d, J = 17.8 Hz, 1 H), 3.79 (s, 3 H), 3.83 (s, 3 H), 4.60 (s, 1 H), 5.50 (s, 1 H), 6.26 (s, 1 H), 6.33 (s, 1 H); $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (125 MHz, CDCl_3): δ = 21.8, 21.9, 24.9, 34.2, 37.0, 37.7, 48.1, 55.3, 55.5, 72.5, 83.6, 96.5, 100.0, 104.2, 115.7, 136.3, 160.2, 160.8; ESIMS (MeOH): 325.2 ($[M + \text{Na}]^+$, 100); HRESIMS: m/z calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_4\text{Na}$: 325.1416; found: 325.1426.

9.3. Reductive cleavage of domino products 8c and 9c. Synthesis of 10c and 11c.

9.3.1. Reductive cleavage of domino product 8c.

Reductive cleavage of acetalic compound **8c** (15 mg, 0.040 mmol) using the general procedure afforded after flash chromatography (SiO_2 , heptane/EtOAc, 2:1) compound **10c** (8.4 mg, 66%).

10c: white solid, m.p. = 102-104 °C (*t*BuOMe); IR (film): ν = 3526, 2926, 1608, 1464, 1202, 1148, 1119, 1025, 925, 828 cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (500 MHz, CDCl_3): δ = 1.05-1.11 (m, 2 H), 1.35-1.39 (m, 2 H), 1.42 (d, J = 14.3 Hz, 2 H), 1.57-1.64 (m, 3 H), 1.76 (dt, J = 3.0, 11.9 Hz, 1 H), 2.07 (d, J = 14.8 Hz, 1 H), 2.34-2.41 (m, 1 H), 2.93 (d, J = 14.7 Hz, 1 H), 3.38 (dd, J = 3.5, 8.0 Hz, 1 H), 3.73 (dd, J = 8.0, 10.7 Hz, 1 H), 3.78 (s, 3 H), 3.80 (s, 3 H), 3.85 (dd, J = 3.5, 10.7 Hz, 1 H), 3.96-4.05 (m, 2 H), 6.23 (d, J = 2.5 Hz, 1 H), 6.32 (d, J = 2.5 Hz, 1 H); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (125 MHz, CDCl_3): δ = 20.8, 22.3, 29.7, 34.7, 35.4, 40.4, 42.9, 44.8, 55.2 (2 C), 63.1, 64.1, 84.5, 96.4, 105.0, 116.3, 139.3, 157.6, 158.8; ESIMS (MeOH): 301.2 ($[M - \text{OH}]^+$, 100), 341.2 ($[M + \text{Na}]^+$, 50); HRESIMS: m/z calcd. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_4\text{Na}$: 341.1729; found: 341.1722.

9.3.2. Reductive opening and acetylation of domino product 9c.

Reductive opening of acetalic compound **9c** (20 mg, 0.066 mmol) using the general procedure afforded compound **11c** as a diastereomeric mixture (12.4 mg, 65%). After acetylation (92%), both diastereomers were separated by preparative HPLC, thus obtaining 9.6 mg of *cis*-**11c-Ac** and 3.2 mg of *trans*-**11c-Ac** (3:1 ratio).

cis-**11c-Ac**: colourless oil; IR (film): $\square = 2919, 2850, 1736, 1595, 1463, 1232, 1206, 1145, 1052, 824 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (500 MHz, CDCl_3): $\square = 1.25-1.33$ (m, 3 H), 1.36-1.41 (m, 2 H), 1.50-1.56 (m, 2 H), 1.62-1.68 (m, 5 H), 1.99 (s, 3 H), 2.21 (d, $J = 17.0 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 2.42 (d, $J = 18.0 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 2.72 (dd, $J = 6.4, 18.0 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 3.77 (s, 3 H), 3.78 (s, 3 H), 4.09-4.21 (m, 2 H), 6.20 (d, $J = 1.8 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 6.27 (d, $J = 1.8 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H); $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (125 MHz, CDCl_3): $\square = 21.1, 21.7, 25.9, 26.7, 29.1, 29.7, 33.7, 34.2, 34.8, 37.1, 38.0, 55.1, 55.2, 61.1, 95.8, 104.5, 115.5, 136.2, 158.3, 171.2$; ESIMS (MeOH): 333.2 ($[M + \text{H}]^+$, 100); HRESIMS : m/z calcd. for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{29}\text{O}_4$: 333.2066; found: 333.2056.

trans-**11c-Ac**: colourless oil; IR (film): $\square = 2922, 2852, 1738, 1594, 1454, 1365, 1235, 1145, 1051, 825, 732 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (500 MHz, CDCl_3): $\square = 1.05$ (td, $J = 3.1, 13.3 \text{ Hz}$, 2 H), 1.22-1.36 (m, 3 H+ HDO), 1.40-1.65 (m, 3 H), 1.78-1.87 (m, 3 H), 1.97 (s, 3 H), 2.03-2.09 (m, 1 H), 2.39 (d, $J = 16.7 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 2.59-2.66 (m, 2 H), 3.77 (s, 3 H), 3.78 (s, 3 H), 3.97 (ddd, $J = 6.0, 9.3, 10.7 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 4.17 (ddd, $J = 6.0, 9.3, 10.7 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 6.18 (d, $J = 2.1 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 6.28 (d, $J = 2.1 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H); $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (125 MHz, CDCl_3): $\square = 21.0, 21.9, 23.9, 26.4, 27.0, 28.4, 34.0, 36.3, 42.0, 43.0, 55.2, 55.3, 61.6, 95.8, 104.6, 117.1, 137.3, 157.9, 158.5, 171.2$; ESIMS (MeOH): 333.2 ($[M + \text{H}]^+$, 100); HRESIMS : m/z calcd. for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{29}\text{O}_4$: 333.2066; found: 333.2066.

9.4. Oxidation of (*cis/trans*)-11c. Synthesis of aldehydes (*cis/trans*)-12c.

Compound **11c** (18 mg, 0.062 mmol) was oxidated by adding DMP (0.150 mmol, 63.1 mg, 2.4 equiv) and pyridine (0.186 mmol, 14.7 mg, 15 μL , 3.0 equiv) in CH_2Cl_2 at 0 °C. The reaction was then allowed to warm to room temperature and stirred for 2h. Usual workup and flash chromatography afforded **12c** (17.3 mg, 84%) in a 3 to 1 *cis/trans* ratio. Both diastereomers were separated by preparative HPLC, thus obtaining 13.0 mg of *cis*-**12c** and 4.3 mg of *trans*-**12c**.

cis-**12c**: colourless oil; IR (film): $\nu = 2923, 2852, 1716, 1608, 1596, 1492, 1464, 1210, 1147, 1092, 1053, 826 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (500 MHz, CDCl_3): $\delta = 1.30\text{-}1.36$ (m, 2 H), 1.42-1.48 (m, 1 H), 1.53-1.62 (m, 3 H), 1.67-1.74 (m, 2 H), 1.75-1.81 (m, 1 H), 2.29-2.40 (m, 3 H), 2.49 (d, $J = 18.0 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 2.73 (dd, $J = 6.7, 18.0 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 3.19 (d, $J = 17.2 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 3.78 (s, 3 H), 3.79 (s, 3 H), 6.22 (d, $J = 2.5 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 6.29 (d, $J = 2.5 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 9.89 (t, $J = 3.1 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H); $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (125 MHz, CDCl_3): $\delta = 21.5$ (2 C), 25.8, 26.6, 28.9, 33.8, 35.8, 38.3, 52.5, 55.2 (2 C), 96.1, 104.4, 115.1, 135.5, 158.5 (2 C), 203.6; ESIMS (MeOH): 289.2 ($[M + \text{Na}]^+$, 100); HRESIMS: m/z calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{25}\text{O}_3$: 289.1804; found: 289.1794.

trans-**12c**: colourless oil; IR (film): $\nu = 2923, 2852, 1718, 1608, 1595, 1492, 1454, 1199, 1147, 1100, 1076, 1052, 826 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (500 MHz, CDCl_3): $\delta = 1.17\text{-}1.32$ (m, 2 H), 1.36 (qt, $J = 3.9, 12.8 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 1.48-1.65 (m, 4 H), 1.82 (d, $J = 12.4 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 1.92-2.05 (m, 2 H), 2.22 (dt, $J = 1.9, 14.6 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 2.52 (ddd, $J = 1.9, 3.7, 14.6 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 2.57 (d, $J = 17.8 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 2.66 (dd, $J = 5.6, 17.8 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 2.90 (d, $J = 17.2 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 3.78 (s, 3 H), 3.79 (s, 3 H), 6.21 (d, $J = 2.5 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 6.29 (d, $J = 2.5 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 9.02 (dd, $J = 2.2, 3.9 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H); $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (125 MHz, CDCl_3): $\delta = 21.6, 26.2, 27.1, 28.5, 29.7, 37.0, 40.6, 41.6, 43.3, 55.2, 55.3, 96.1, 104.5, 116.7, 136.6, 158.0, 158.7, 203.8$; ESIMS (MeOH): 289.2 ($[M + \text{Na}]^+$, 100); HRESIMS: m/z calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{25}\text{O}_3$: 289.1804; found: 289.1797.

10. Preparation and domino reactions of substrate-diol **1'd**.

10.1. Preparation of substrate-diol **1'd**.

Xanthate was prepared from the known carbinol (1.8 g, 3.04 mmol) according to general procedure; after purification by flash chromatography (SiO₂, heptane/EtOAc, 95:5) the desired compound (1.70 g, 82%) was obtained and characterized as a diastereomeric mixture. Yellow oil; IR (film): $\nu = 2929, 2856, 1589, 1497, 1462, 1249, 1111, 1063, 1006, 834, 773 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; ESIMS (MeOH): 705.3 ($[M + \text{Na}]^+$, 100); HRESIMS: m/z calcd. for C₃₄H₅₈O₆S₂Si₂Na: 705.3111; found: 705.3121.

Deoxygenation of the xanthate according to the general procedure starting from 1.69 g, (2.47 mmol) afforded after purification by flash chromatography (SiO₂, heptane/EtOAc, 95:5) the deoxygenated TBS-protected diol (1.37 g, 96%), characterized as a diastereomeric mixture. IR (film): $\nu = 2929, 2855, 1588, 1497, 1462, 1248, 1112, 1008, 834, 774 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; ESIMS (MeOH): 599.4 ($[M + \text{Na}]^+$, 100); HRESIMS: m/z calcd. for C₃₂H₅₆O₅Si₂Na: 599.3564; found: 599.3554.

Fluoride deprotection of the latter (1.35 g, 2.34 mmol) using the general procedure (5h) gave after flash chromatography (SiO₂, heptane/EtOAc, 1:1) the substrate-diol **1'd** (628 mg, 77%), which was characterized as a diastereomeric mixture.

1'd: colourless oil; IR (film): $\nu = 3391, 2929, 1589, 1507, 1457, 1420, 1329, 1238, 1124, 1054, 1007, 907, 726 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; ¹H-NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃): $\delta = 0.78\text{-}1.19$ (m, 2 H), $1.19\text{-}1.40$ (m, 2 H), $1.51\text{-}1.92$ (m, 5 H), $2.04\text{-}2.16$ (m, 1 H), $2.20\text{-}2.37$ (m, 1 H), 2.69 (d, $J = 13.7 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 2.81 (d, $J = 13.5 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), $3.17\text{-}3.42$ (m, 3 H), 3.47 (ddd, $J = 3.9, 7.9, 12.6 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), $3.75\text{-}3.84$ (m, 9 H), 3.96 (d, $J = 7.5 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 5.22 (s, 1 H), 6.33 (s, 2 H); ¹³C-NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃): $\delta = 21.6, 28.1, 31.4, 38.7, 40.3, 40.9, 41.3, 56.2$ (2 C), $60.8, 70.1, 74.7, 107.6$ (2 C), $122.4, 134.2, 136.5, 145.2, 152.6$ (2 C); ESIMS (MeOH): 371.2 ($[M + \text{Na}]^+$, 100); HRESIMS: m/z calcd. for C₂₀H₂₈O₅Na: 371.1834; found: 371.1832.

¹³C-NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃): $\delta = 21.6, 28.1, 31.4, 38.7, 40.3, 40.9, 41.3, 56.2$ (2 C), $60.8, 70.1, 74.7, 107.6$ (2 C), $122.4, 134.2, 136.5, 145.2, 152.6$ (2 C); ESIMS (MeOH): 371.2 ($[M + \text{Na}]^+$, 100); HRESIMS: m/z calcd. for C₂₀H₂₈O₅Na: 371.1834; found: 371.1832.

10.2. Domino reactions. Synthesis of 2'd and 5d.

10.2.1. Interrupted cascade.

The oxidative cleavage of **1'd** (125 mg, 0.359 mmol, diastereomeric mixture), using method A over 4 h, afforded after flash chromatography (SiO_2 , heptane/EtOAc, 4:1) 101.9 mg (82%) of domino product **2'd**.

Half-cascade domino product 2'd: colourless oil; IR (film): $\nu = 2929, 1589, 1507, 1420, 1237, 1213, 1125, 1054, 1010, 795, 783 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (500 MHz, CDCl_3): $\delta = 1.18\text{-}1.27$ (m, 1 H), $1.32\text{-}1.40$ (m, 2 H), $1.42\text{-}1.50$ (m, 2 H), $1.54\text{-}1.61$ (m, 2 H), 1.79 (dd, $J = 5.8, 13.8$ Hz, 1 H), 2.02 (d, $J = 14.3$ Hz, 1 H), 2.33 (d, $J = 13.7$ Hz, 1 H), 2.64 (d, $J = 13.5$ Hz, 1 H), 2.89 (d, $J = 13.6$ Hz, 1 H), $3.80\text{-}3.82$ (m, 9 H), 4.85 (d, $J = 6.0$ Hz, 1 H), 5.65 (d, $J = 5.7$ Hz, 1 H), 6.25 (d, $J = 6.2$ Hz, 1 H), 6.33 (s, 2 H); $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (75 MHz, CDCl_3): $\delta = 20.6, 21.1, 29.2, 30.0, 36.5, 48.6, 53.9, 56.0$ (2 C), $60.7, 82.2, 99.3, 106.7$ (2 C), $109.8, 135.1, 136.4, 139.5, 152.8$ (2 C); ESIMS (MeOH): 347.2 ($[M + \text{H}]^+$, 100); HRESIMS: m/z calcd. for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{27}\text{O}_5$: 347.1858; found: 347.1856.

10.2.2. Domino product.

Applying domino conditions on **2'd** (90 mg, 0.26 mmol), using method D over 20h, afforded after flash chromatography (SiO_2 , heptane/EtOAc, 2:1) deoxygenated full cascade **5d** (71.4 mg, 68%).

Domino product 5d: white solid, mp: 147-150 °C (*t*BuOMe); IR (film): $\nu = 2934, 2856, 1740, 1600, 1494, 1459, 1230, 1119, 1039, 922 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (500 MHz, C_6D_6): $\delta = 0.85\text{-}0.98$ (m, 1 H), 1.11-1.24 (m, 2 H), 1.24-1.32 (m, 3 H), 1.58 (m, $J = 12.9$ Hz, 1 H), 1.73-1.81 (m, 4 H), 1.98-2.05 (m, 2 H), 2.57 (d, $J = 18.0$ Hz, 1 H), 2.76 (d, $J = 18.0$ Hz, 1 H), 3.40 (s, 3 H), 3.56 (d, $J = 5.4$ Hz, 1 H), 3.69 (s, 3 H), 3.79 (s, 3 H), 5.51 (d, $J = 5.4$ Hz, 1 H), 6.17 (s, 1 H), 6.43 (d, $J = 5.4$ Hz, 1 H); $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (125 MHz, C_6D_6): $\delta = 18.0, 18.3, 19.2, 29.6, 34.6, 36.7, 36.8, 42.4, 47.8, 52.5, 57.4, 57.8, 78.1, 90.0, 95.0, 104.5, 118.7, 127.8, 138.2, 149.6, 150.5, 166.2$; ESIMS (MeOH): 345.2 ($[M - \text{OAc}]^+$, 100), 427.2 ($[M + \text{Na}]^+$, 10); HRESIMS: m/z calcd. for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}_7\text{Na}$: 427.1733; found: 427.1737.

11. Preparation and domino reactions of substrate-diol 1'f.

11.1. Preparation of substrate-diol 1'f.

Xanthate was prepared from the known carbinol (1.9 g, 3.58 mmol) according to general procedure; after purification by flash chromatography (SiO_2 , heptane) the desired compound (1.80 g, 81%) was obtained and characterized as a diastereomeric mixture. Colourless oil; IR (film): $\nu = 2928, 2856, 1472, 1463, 1251, 1215, 1060, 833, 773 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; ESIMS (MeOH): 553.4 (100), 643.3 ($[M + \text{Na}]^+$, 15); HRESIMS: m/z calcd. for $\text{C}_{33}\text{H}_{56}\text{O}_3\text{S}_2\text{Si}_2\text{Na}$: 643.3107; found: 643.3097.

Deoxygenation of the xanthate according to the general procedure and starting from 1.80 g (2.90 mmol), afforded after purification by flash chromatography (SiO_2 , heptane/EtOAc, 99:1) the deoxygenated TBS-protected diol (1.46 g, 98%), which was characterized as a diastereomeric mixture. Colourless oil; IR (film): $\nu = 2928, 2856, 1472, 1462, 1250, 1089, 1062, 833, 772 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; ESIMS (MeOH): 310.2 (100), 532.4 ($[M + \text{Na}]^+$, 40); HRESIMS: m/z calcd. for $\text{C}_{33}\text{H}_{55}\text{O}_5\text{S}_2\text{Si}_2\text{Na}$: 532.4006; found: 532.3999.

Fluoride deprotection of the latter (1.40 g, 2.72 mmol) using the general procedure (5h) gave after flash chromatography (SiO_2 , heptane/EtOAc, 1:1) the substrate-diol 1'f (421 mg, 54%). Characterized as a diastereomeric mixture. Colourless oil; IR (film): $\nu = 3351, 2925, 2858, 1603, 1457, 1054, 908, 842, 731, 695 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; ESIMS (MeOH): 186.2 (100), 304.2 ($[M + \text{NH}_4]^+$, 90); HRESIMS: m/z calcd. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{30}\text{NO}_2$: 304.2277; found: 304.2263.

11.2. Domino reactions. Synthesis of 2'f and 5f.

11.2.1. Interrupted cascade.

The oxidative cleavage of **1'f** (100 mg, 0.349 mmol, diastereomeric mixture), using method A over 4h, afforded after flash chromatography (SiO_2 , heptane/EtOAc, 9:1) 83.4 mg (84%) of domino product **2'f**.

Half-cascade domino product 2'f: white solid, m.p. = 135-138 °C (*t*BuOMe); IR (film): $\nu = 2924, 2854, 1729, 1458, 1377, 1367, 1285, 1174, 1114, 1073, 1041, 846 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (300 MHz, CDCl_3): $\delta = 1.17\text{-}1.67$ (m, 7 H), 1.74 (dd, $J = 5.8, 13.7$ Hz, 1 H), 2.05 (d, $J = 12.5$ Hz, 1 H), 2.23 (s, 6 H), 2.38 (d, $J = 13.8$ Hz, 1 H), 2.66 (d, $J = 13.3$ Hz, 1 H), 2.91 (d, $J = 13.3$ Hz, 1 H), 4.89 (d, $J = 6.1$ Hz, 1 H), 5.67 (d, $J = 5.6$ Hz, 1 H), 6.28 (d, $J = 6.0$ Hz, 1 H), 6.78 (bs, 2 H), 6.86 (bs, 1 H); $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (75 MHz, CDCl_3): $\delta = 20.7, 21.2, 21.3$ (2 C), 29.3, 31.1, 35.7, 48.3, 53.9, 82.4, 99.4, 110.1, 127.7 (2 C), 137.5 (3 C), 139.4, 139.5.

11.2.2. Domino product.

Applying domino conditions on **2'f** (85 mg, 0.300 mmol), using method D over 20h, afforded after flash chromatography (SiO_2 , heptane/EtOAc, 4:1) deoxygenated full cascade **5f** (74.7 mg, 73%).

Domino product 5f: white solid, m.p. = 89-92 °C (*t*BuOMe); IR (film): $\nu = 2925, 2855, 1760, 1450, 1366, 1224, 1059, 1042, 1027, 961, 920, 796, 731 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; $^1\text{H-NMR}$

(500 MHz, CDCl₃): δ = 0.99-1.19 (m, 2 H), 1.33-1.53 (m, 4 H), 1.42-1.48 (m, 1 H), 1.78-1.69 (m, 1 H), 1.86 (d, J = 14.0 Hz, 1 H), 2.05 (s, 3 H), 2.26 (s, 3 H), 2.28-2.32 (m, 4 H), 2.89 (d, J = 18.5 Hz, 1 H), 3.14 (d, J = 7.8 Hz, 1 H), 3.36 (d, J = 18.4 Hz, 1 H), 5.54 (dd, J = 2.0, 4.3 Hz, 1 H), 5.85 (d, J = 8.0 Hz, 1 H), 6.79 (bs, 1 H), 6.81 (s, 1 H); ¹H-NMR (500 MHz, C₆D₆): δ = 0.78 (q, J = 13.6 Hz, 1 H), 1.04 (dt, J = 5.4, 14.0 Hz, 1 H), 1.10-1.16 (m, 1 H), 1.17-1.26 (m, 2 H), 1.31-1.39 (m, 1 H), 1.47 (ddd, J = 12.3, 12.9, 13.4 Hz, 1 H), 1.57 (s, 3 H), 1.81-1.89 (m, 2 H), 2.07 (d, J = 14.4 Hz, 1 H), 2.11 (s, 3 H), 2.23 (s, 3 H), 2.54 (d, J = 18.5 Hz, 1 H), 3.03 (d, J = 18.4 Hz, 1 H), 3.26 (d, J = 8.0 Hz, 1 H), 5.47 (d, J = 5.8 Hz, 1 H), 6.24 (d, J = 8.0 Hz, 1 H), 6.60 (s, 1 H), 6.71 (s, 1 H); ¹³C-NMR (75 MHz, C₆D₆): δ = 16.4, 17.5, 18.0, 18.2, 19.0, 28.6, 36.4, 36.5, 38.2, 44.1, 48.8, 79.3, 89.6, 95.5, 124.2, 126.2, 128.7, 133.1, 133.3, 133.6, 165.7; ESIMS (MeOH): 283.2 ($[M - \text{AcO}]^+$, 100), 365.2 ($[M + \text{Na}]^+$, 35); HRESIMS: m/z calcd. for C₂₁H₂₆O₄Na: 365.1729; found: 365.1722.

12. Preparation and domino reactions of substrate-diol **1'i**.

12.1. Preparation of substrate-diol **1'i**.

Xanthate was prepared from the known carbinol (1.5 g, 2.98 mmol) according to the general procedure; after purification by flash chromatography (SiO₂, heptane/EtOAc, 99:1) the desired compound (1.53 g, 87%) was obtained and characterized as a diastereomeric mixture. Yellow oil; IR (film): ν = 2928, 2856, 1472, 1463, 1251, 1217, 1201, 1058, 831, 772, cm⁻¹; ESIMS (MeOH): 615.3 ($[M + \text{Na}]^+$, 100); HRESIMS: m/z calcd. for C₃₁H₅₂O₃S₂Si₂Na: 615.2794; found: 615.2786.

Deoxygenation of the xanthate according to the general procedure and starting from 1.5 g (2.53 mmol), afforded after purification by flash chromatography (SiO₂, heptane/EtOAc, 99:1) the deoxygenated TBS-protected diol (1.22 g, 99%), which was characterized as a diastereomeric mixture. Colourless oil; IR (film): ν = 2928, 2856, 1472, 1462, 1250, 1092, 1065, 831, 772, 734, 701 cm⁻¹; ESIMS (MeOH): 509.3 ($[M + \text{Na}]^+$, 100); HRESIMS: m/z calcd. for C₂₉H₅₀O₂Si₂Na: 509.3247; found: 509.3245.

Fluoride deprotection of the latter (1.20 g, 2.46 mmol) using the general procedure (5h) gave after flash chromatography (SiO₂, heptane/EtOAc, 1:1) the substrate-diol **1'i** (490 mg, 77%) which was characterized as a diastereomeric mixture. Colourless oil; IR (film): ν = 3361, 2927, 2857, 1455, 1059, 985, 754, 706 cm⁻¹.

12.2. Domino reactions. Synthesis of 2'i, 5i and 6i.

12.2.1. Interrupted cascade.

Oxidative cleavage of **1'i** (100 mg, 0.387 mmol, diastereomeric mixture), using method A over 4 h, afforded after flash chromatography (SiO_2 , heptane/EtOAc, 9:1) 85 mg (85%) of domino product **2'i**.

Half-cascade domino product 2'i: white solid, m.p. = 88-90 °C (Et_2O); IR (film): $\nu = 2923, 1629, 1453, 1212, 1054, 935, 700 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (300 MHz, CDCl_3): $\delta = 1.24$ (td, $J = 4.8, 13.5 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 1.33-1.52 (m, 3 H), 1.52-1.68 (m, 3 H), 1.74 (dd, $J = 5.8, 13.9 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 2.07 (d, $J = 18.3 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 2.39 (d, $J = 13.8 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 2.75 (d, $J = 13.4 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 3.00 (d, $J = 13.4 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 4.91 (d, $J = 6.1 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 5.68 (d, $J = 5.7 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 6.29 (d, $J = 6.1 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 7.14-7.37 (m, 5 H); $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (50 MHz, CDCl_3): $\delta = 20.7, 21.1, 29.3, 31.0, 35.9, 48.3, 53.9, 82.3, 99.4, 110.0, 126.0, 128.1$ (2 C), 129.8 (2 C), 139.4, 139.5; ESIMS (MeOH): 257.2 ($[M + \text{H}]^+$, 100); HRESIMS: m/z calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{21}\text{O}_2$: 257.1542; found: 257.1534.

12.2.2. Domino products 5i and 6i.

Domino reaction over **2i** (40 mg, 0.16 mmol) employing method C –MW heating at 70 °C– gave a mixture of deoxygenated full cascade **5i** (8.8 mg, 18%) and ring expansion cascade **6i** (30.3 mg, 52%).

Applying domino conditions on **2i** (150 mg, 0.58 mmol), using method D over 20h, afforded after flash chromatography (SiO_2 , heptane/EtOAc, 4:1), a mixture of deoxygenated full cascade **5i** (130.5 mg, 71%) and ring expansion cascade **6i** (35.0 mg, 16%).

Domino product 5i: white solid, m.p. = 129-132 °C (*t*BuOMe); IR (film): $\nu = 2935, 2858, 1760, 1452, 1222, 1177, 1137, 1044, 979, 961, 923 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (500 MHz, CDCl_3): $\delta = 1.22$ (tt, $J = 3.5, 12.8 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 1.32 (td, $J = 5.3, 14.6 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 1.42 - 1.48 (m, 1 H), 1.49 - 1.68 (m, 4 H), 1.97 (d, $J = 14.7 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 2.11 (s, 3 H), 2.17 (d, $J = 1.6 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 2.19 (d, $J = 5.2 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 2.95 (d, $J = 5.2 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 3.04 (d, $J = 18.3 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 3.12 (d, $J = 18.5 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 5.55 (dd, $J = 1.6, 5.3 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 5.98 (d, $J = 5.3 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 7.11 - 7.16 (m, 2 H), 7.17 - 7.21 (m, 2 H); $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (75 MHz, CDCl_3): $\delta = 20.8, 21.3, 21.8, 32.4, 36.3, 39.0, 39.7, 49.5, 50.6, 81.1, 94.0, 98.1, 126.3, 127.4, 128.8, 129.5, 134.6, 135.0, 170.0$; ESIMS (MeOH): 337.1 ($[M + \text{Na}]^+$, 50) 378.2 ($[M + \text{Na} + \text{CH}_3\text{CN}]^+$, 100); HRESIMS: m/z calcd. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_4\text{Na}$: 337.1416; found: 337.1423.

Domino product 6i: white solid, m.p. = 131-134 °C (*t*BuOMe); IR (film): $\nu = 2927, 1756, 1453, 1368, 1215, 1049, 1008, 948, 920, 704 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (500 MHz,

CDCl₃): δ = 1.55-1.60 (m, 2 H), 1.63-1.70 (m, 2 H), 1.74-1.80 (m, 1 H), 1.83-1.90 (m, 3 H), 2.11 (s, 3 H), 2.12, (s, 3 H), 2.60-2.72 (m, 2 H), 2.86 (d, J = 13.6 Hz, 1 H), 2.94 (d, J = 4.1 Hz, 1 H), 3.11 (d, J = 13.6 Hz, 1 H), 6.32 (dd, J = 3.5, 6.5 Hz, 1 H), 6.41 (d, J = 4.0 Hz, 1 H), 7.12 (d, J = 7.7 Hz, 2 H), 7.24-7.28 (m, 1 H), 7.31 (dd, J = 6.4, 7.4 Hz, 2 H); ¹³C-NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃): δ = 21.1, 21.2, 23.4, 24.0, 37.0, 37.1, 37.3, 44.3, 45.9, 56.6, 89.9, 90.9, 126.9, 128.4 (2 C), 130.8 (2 C), 136.1, 168.8, 169.1, 209.2; ESIMS (MeOH): 397.2 ($[M + Na]^+$, 100), 771.3 ($[2M + Na]^+$, 55); HRESIMS: m/z calcd. for C₂₁H₂₆O₆Na: 397.1627; found: 397.1617.

13. X-ray structures for reported compounds.

4j

5i

8c

9c

trans-12c

14. Crystallographic data for reported compounds.

Table 2: X-Rays diffraction data for reported monocrystals. Recorded in «Nonius KappaCCD» or «Rigaku rapid II RAXIS» diffractometers.

COMPOUND	4j	5i	8c
Empirical formula	C ₂₀ H ₂₄ O ₆	C ₁₉ H ₂₂ O ₄	C ₂₁ H ₂₆ O ₆
Formula weight	360.39	314.37	374.42
Temperature (K)	293(2)	193(2)	293(2)
Wavelength (Å)	0.71069	1.54187	0.71070
Crystal system, space group	Orthorhombic P _{bca}	Monoclinic P _{21/c}	Monoclinic P _{21/c}
Unit cell dimensions (Å)	a = 13.454(6) b = 14.264(6) c = 18.774(8)	a = 8.934(3) b = 16.842(4) c = 10.578(8)	a = 12.053(2) b = 8.6810(10) c = 21.298(2)
(°)	$\alpha = \beta = \gamma = 90$	$\beta = 91.22(4)$ $\alpha = \gamma = 90$	$\beta = 119.86(4)$ $\alpha = \gamma = 90$
Volume (Å ³)	3603(3)	1591.3(14)	1932.6(9)
Z, Z' Calc. density (g/cm ³)	8, 1.329	4, 1.312	4, 1.287
Absorp. coeff. (mm ⁻¹)	0.098	0.739	0.094
F(000)	1536	672	800
Crystal size (mm)	0.48 x 0.48 x 0.38	0.35 x 0.28 x 0.20	0.48 x 0.25 x 0.21
θ range for data collect° (°)	3.01 to 26.36	4.94 to 68.14	3.14 to 25.32
Limiting indices	-16 ≤ h ≤ 16, -17 ≤ k ≤ 17, -23 ≤ l ≤ 23	-10 ≤ h ≤ 10, -17 ≤ k ≤ 20, -12 ≤ l ≤ 12	-14 ≤ h ≤ 14, -10 ≤ k ≤ 10, -25 ≤ l ≤ 25
Refl° collected / unique	31435 / 3664 [R(int) = 0.0217]	10106 / 2810 [R(int) = 0.0455]	30762 / 3516 [R(int) = 0.0162]
Completeness to θ_{\max}	99.6%	96.5%	99.3%
Refinement method	Full-matrix least-squares on F ²		
Data / restr. / param.	3664 / 0 / 238	2810 / 0 / 209	3516 / 0 / 258
Goodness of fit	1.047	1.095	1.044
Final R indices [I > 2s(I)]	R1 = 0.0434 wR2 = 0.1021	R1 = 0.0553 wR2 = 0.1591	R1 = 0.0551 wR2 = 0.1478
R indices (all data)	R1 = 0.0662 wR2 = 0.1145	R1 = 0.0707 wR2 = 0.1728	R1 = 0.0769 wR2 = 0.1655
Largest Δ peak/hole (e.Å ⁻³)	0.190 and -0.151	0.275 and -0.277	0.285 and -0.192

COMPOUND	9c	trans-12c
Empirical formula	C ₁₈ H ₂₂ O ₄	C ₁₈ H ₂₄ O ₃
Formula weight	302.36	288.37
Temperature (K)	293(2)	293(2)
Wavelength (Å)	0.71069	0.71070
Crystal system, space group	Monoclinic P _{21/c}	Monoclinic P _{21/c}
Unit cell dimensions (Å)	a = 7.381(2) b = 16.417(5) c = 12.721(3)	a = 22.7180(10) b = 8.3040(10) c = 17.6000(10)
(°)	β = 93.964(4) α = γ = 90	β = 108.32(5) α = γ = 90
Volume (Å ³)	1537.8(7)	3152.0(4)
Z, Z' Calc. density (g/cm ³)	4, 1.306	8, 1.215
Absorp. coeff. (mm ⁻¹)	0.091	0.081
F(000)	648	1248
Crystal size (mm)	0.40 x 0.28 x 0.08	0.10 x 0.10 x 0.10
θ range for data collect° (°)	2.96 to 25.05	2.32 to 22.47
Limiting indices	-8 ≤ h ≤ 8, -19 ≤ k ≤ 18, -15 ≤ l ≤ 15	-24 ≤ h ≤ 24, -8 ≤ k ≤ 8, -18 ≤ l ≤ 18
Refl° collected / unique	4647 / 2705 [R(int) = 0.0231]	6474/3852 [R(int) = 0.0475]
Completeness to θ _{max}	99.4%	94.0%
Refinement method	Full-matrix least-squares on F ²	
Data / restr. / param.	2705 / 0 / 202	3852 / 0 / 383
Goodness of fit	1.035	1.117
Final R indices [I > 2σ(I)]	R1 = 0.0484 wR2 = 0.1485	R1 = 0.0779 wR2 = 0.1593
R indices (all data)	R1 = 0.0766 wR2 = 0.1326	R1 = 0.1244 wR2 = 0.1813
Largest Δpeak/hole (e.Å ⁻³)	0.225 and -0.154	0.262 and -0.219